

**Sport for development and education: Addressing inequity
through participant engagement, inclusive practice, and
transformational pedagogy**

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Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements of the University of the West of
Scotland for the award of Doctor of Philosophy

April 2022

Declarations

I, David William Meir declare that the thesis has not been submitted for a DBA, DProf, EngD or PhD or comparable academic award. As part of this thesis two co authored published articles have been submitted. I declare that I am the lead author on both submitted articles and conducted all primary data collection.

Personal details withheld.

Acknowledgements

I would firstly like to thank my supervisors, Professor David McGillivray and Dr Sandro Carnicelli for their wise words, support and guidance throughout an enjoyable and engaging process. Secondly, I thank those who have supported me with my research, those who have participated within it, and the scholars who have influenced my thinking over the years. Finally, to Emma who is a brilliant mum and an amazing wife.

Abstract

The aim of this appraisal is to critically reflect upon the published articles and explore ways in which education in sport for development should be designed, delivered, and analysed. In response to this position, I reflect on my personal and professional experiences in sport for development and education and the political and philosophical perspectives that have informed my research. The reflections will explore the influence of these experiences and perspectives on the geographical, social, cultural, and political complexities within the published articles. Through a critical and reflective appraisal, the published articles are synthesised into a coherent body of knowledge. The reflection is framed through the generation of four themes. These are (1) participant engagement and outcomes (2) addressing inequity (3) inclusion for social justice and (4) transformational pedagogy. The critical and reflective appraisal informs a concise summary that outlines the published articles contribution, reflects on what I have learned throughout the process and explores how that knowledge could be applied in the future in the design, delivery and analysis of education within sport for development projects.

PhD by Publication – Guidance for examiners

Firstly, I would like to express my gratitude for your agreement to be an examiner for my PhD by publication. I know how difficult it is to find time in academia and your contribution to this process is greatly appreciated. The reason for this opening statement is to clarify the approach to reviewing the different documents within this PhD. Due to this being a PhD by publication the articles have been collated in a separate document and I believe it would be beneficial for you to read the published articles prior to accessing the critical appraisal. The articles are presented in a linear way, and it is my advice that they are read in that way, to show how the key themes within the articles have developed over the last five years.

Thanks again, and I look forward to questions and discussions at the viva examination.

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Chapter 1 - Introduction

If sport practitioners are to be serious about development, they need to figure out what they believe development should be and construct sport programs and education initiatives designed specifically to address these ideals and objectives (Hartmann & Kwauk, 2011, pp. 298).

My published articles focus on two distinct yet connected areas: sport for development (SfD) and education. This appraisal will explore their interconnectivity and through this, their potential to address inequity, promote inclusive practice and inform pedagogy in SfD. Whilst my published articles have explored SfD and education this critical appraisal will be SfD focused. The rationale for this intention is the limited analysis of education in SfD scholarship. It is my view that to address this limitation requires the incorporation of knowledge from across education, education development and physical education. An increased knowledge and understanding of different education disciplines will provide a deeper understanding of the processes and practices that would enhance education in SfD. To address these concerns, the aim of this critical appraisal is to synthesis and analysis my published work and relevant literature from SfD and education to develop new perspectives in the design, delivery, and analysis of education within SfD.

1.1 Introducing Sport for Development and Education

SfD is the utilisation of sport as a tool for development to address wider social issues and contribute to a variety of different circumstances and contexts (Kidd, 2008). SfD is a global project that takes shape differently in diverse geographical locations and contexts. Svensson & Woods (2017) identified 944 current SfD organisations. Just under 70% of these organisations operate within the global South with over 40% in Africa with rest operating in Latin America (10.5%), Asia (12.2%) and the Middle East (2.8%). SfD in these diverse locations and contexts

is inevitably affected by wider social, historical, and cultural factors. SfD organisations and local actors are connected to differing aspects of local cultural contexts yet are also affected both directly and indirectly by wider forces (Lindsey & Grattan, 2012). In the context of this critical appraisal, SfD should be considered in terms of its capacity to work across, and within, other development categories specifically, education (Levermore, 2008). There are however, concerns with the way in which education is designed and delivered within SfD. These concerns are reinforced through inequitable, paternalistic and dependent approaches to learning which have struggled to advance the position of marginalised communities (Hayhurst, 2009; Bloch, 2009). Further to this concern is the limited critical analysis of pedagogical strategies employed in the realisation of intended social change outcomes (Schweisfurth, 2015). When conventional approaches to pedagogy are applied in SfD they are entrenched through global North designed and orientated pedagogy that focus on increasing personal skills and attributes whilst overlooking wider issues such as history, culture, politics, and power (Mwaanga & Prince, 2016).

One way of realising social change through SfD is the development and delivery of equitable and inclusive education programmes. Equity considers the social justice ramifications of education in relation to fairness, justness, and impartiality (Jacob and Holsinger, 2008). In support of an equitable approach to education, inclusion is *'the primary mechanism to break the structural inequalities that impede sustainable development and prevent social cohesion'* (UNESCO, 2015, p.20). An inclusive approach requires an in-built flexibility that gives practitioners freedom to adapt their working methods to achieve maximum impact and relevance within a specific context (UNESCO, 2015).

The importance of equity and inclusion have been reinforced through *'Transforming our World: the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development'* (UNESCO, 2015). Within the 2030 Agenda there is no specific Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) for sport. The United

Nations does, however, recognise that sport is an important enabler of sustainable development through its promotion of tolerance and respect alongside its contribution to gender equality, education, social inclusion, and health. A significant goal for SfD is SDG4: *'Ensure Inclusive and Equitable Quality Education and Promote Lifelong Learning Opportunities for All'*. Education is a central part of SDG4 which reinforces issues around inclusion, lifelong learning, and relevant and effective learning outcomes through appropriate pedagogical implementation.

A transformative pedagogical approach that can address the requirements of SDG4 is critical pedagogy. Its purpose is to address the workings of power through the way in which knowledge is produced, distributed, and consumed. Implementing critical pedagogy within SfD education would enable political, social, and economic factors to be addressed (Macedo, 1994), and challenges the practices that are taken for granted within dominant culture and conventional educational practice (Gruenewald, 2003). The relevance of critical pedagogy is reinforced by UNESCO (2016, p.18) who state that the principles of equity and inclusion are not only about ensuring access to education but also about having *'pedagogies that enable students to thrive, understand their realities and to work for a more just society'*. Adopting critical pedagogy within SfD requires organisations to actively engage participants in a mutual process of grappling with power, inequality, and identity alongside challenging their own assumptions of sport, education, and development. This would ensure that desired development outcomes are in tune with local conditions, aspirations and needs (Lindsey & Darby, 2019).

I have discussed key aspects of culture, geographical location, equity, inclusion and pedagogy within SfD due to their relevance to the published articles and therefore, this critical appraisal. Having introduced these key aspects I now introduce the published articles and discuss how they have explored these aspects across SfD and education.

1.2 Introducing the published articles

This section introduces the published articles through a reflection on my initial engagement with both education and SfD research and how this has evolved theoretically and methodologically. The published articles contribute to four main thematic areas which guide the structure of both this section and the remainder of the critical appraisal. These are: (1) participant engagement and outcomes (2) addressing inequity (3) inclusion for social justice and (4) transformational pedagogy.

The themes were generated through the synthesis and analysis of my published articles and reflections on my personal development in both research and practice. Participant engagement and outcomes was generated through articles that have called for and engaged with participatory research in SfD and, the understanding that the development and realisation of relevant programme outcomes are directly connected to participant engagement. Addressing inequity derived from personal reflection on all the published articles and the understanding that to realise social change through SfD requires an equitable approach to education that seeks to directly address power disparities. Inclusion has been the most significant influence on my professional practice and research. It has been an ever present and continuously informs my thinking on both SfD and education. Through reflecting on its influence and its impact I have explored its obvious connection with social justice; they are interconnected and therefore inclusive education in SfD cannot be realised without embracing the principles of social justice. Finally, transformational pedagogy was generated over time through the understanding that for SfD to engage participants, address inequity, promote inclusion for social justice and, achieve relevant outcomes a pedagogy is required that enables participants to understand their lived reality and engage collectively in the realisation of positive social change.

The articles, including the title, description of data capture, candidate contribution and thematic areas are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Details of published work

List of Public Outputs	Where & When work was carried out.	Candidate Contribution to public outputs.	Article Reference	Themes
Meir, D (2017) "Leadership and empowerment through sport" The intentions, hopes, ambitions and reality of creating a sport-for-development organisation in Cape Town. <i>Journal of Sport for Development</i> : 5 (8), 19-29	Data collection was carried out in 2016 in Cape Town.	This is a single authored paper	JSFD (2017)	1, 3 & 4
Meir, D (2018) Further education and inclusive practice: past experiences, current issues and future concerns, <i>Research in Post-Compulsory Education</i> , 23 (3), 328-347	Data collection was carried out between 2015 & 2016 in Blackburn.	This is a single authored paper	RPCE (2018)	1 & 2
Meir, D & Fletcher, T (2019) The transformative potential of using participatory community sport initiatives to promote social cohesion in divided community contexts, <i>International Review for the Sociology of Sport</i> , 54 (2), 218-238	Data collection was carried out between 2016 & 2017 in Blackburn.	I am the lead author on the paper and undertook all data collection.	IRSS (2019)	1 & 4
Meir, D & Fletcher, T (2020) The physical education and sport premium: Social justice, autonomy and school sport policy in	Data collection was carried out between 2017 & 2018 in Blackburn.	I am the lead author on the paper and undertook all data collection.	IJSPP (2020)	1 & 2

England, <i>International Journal of Sport Policy and Politics</i> , 12 (2), 237-253				
Meir, D (2022) A qualitative systematic review of critical pedagogy in Physical Education and Sport for Development: exploring a dialogical and critical future for Sport for Development pedagogy, <i>Sport, Education and Society</i> , 27 (3), 300-319	This was a desk-based study carried out at the University of the West of Scotland between 2018 & 2020	This is a single authored paper	SES (2022)	1, 2 & 3

My original engagement with education research focused on inclusive practice (further education) and social justice (physical education). It was, at least from my own perspective, natural to explore the possibilities for transferring the principal elements of my education experience and research into a SfD context. My interest and engagement with SfD and education research has evolved over the years to incorporate understanding of specific pedagogies, theoretical frameworks and methodologies that have sought to address inequity across sport, development, and education. The theoretical frameworks that have been applied in my work are inclusive practice (Ainscow, 1999), social transformation (Castles, 2001), a Theory of Justice (Rawls, 1971), and critical pedagogy (Freire, 1972). In the published articles I have employed predominantly qualitative methodologies. These have included qualitative case study, participatory action research (PAR), analytical auto-ethnography, and qualitative systematic review.

In applying these theoretical frameworks and qualitative methodologies, I have developed an inherently political lens. It has always been the intention to position my work within the middle of power and politics. The rationale for such an approach is twofold. Firstly, SfD programmes,

and therefore the educational aspects within them, are engulfed in political tension, historical baggage, and the management of modern-day diplomacy within the culture of aid, development and more broadly sport (Collison et al, 2016). Secondly, education and by association, physical education, is inherently political. From my perspective, both the structure of education systems and the society in which they sit must be held up to rigorous questioning. If not, education will reinforce existing inequities through re-producing a social system that privileges some while marginalising and repressing others (Craig & Mellor, 2010).

In two of the published articles, I have addressed the issue of inequity in education through a focus on inclusion and social justice. JPCE (2018) and IJSPP (2020) critically explored power disparities between policy at the macro level and their impact on practice at the micro level. I argued that there was a need for clearer understanding of the impact of policies to develop alternative solutions that would address the disparities being reinforced. Similarly, my SfD research has sought to address power disparities that exist in the design, development, and delivery of SfD programmes, with a specific focus on pedagogy. From a macro perspective this has manifested itself in an exploration of the disparity that exists between the educational intentions of global North based SfD organisations, programmes and their participants based in the global South. I argue that the dominance of global North based SfD organisations has limited the capacity for ownership and autonomy at the micro level (JSFD, 2017; SES, 2022). Power disparities, although contextually different, were also in evidence in the research of a participant centred community project that sought to address social cohesion in Blackburn, UK (IRSS, 2019). Based upon the empirical findings within the published articles, I contend that the realisation of equity, inclusion, and social justice within SfD requires a critical shift in policy, practice, and pedagogy that embraces dialogue, reflection, negotiation, and collaboration.

Having introduced the published articles, reflected on my engagement with education and SfD research and discussed how this has evolved I will now introduce the aim and objectives of this critical appraisal.

1.3 Introducing the critical appraisal

The aim of this critical appraisal is to reflect upon a body of published articles and the contribution they have made to addressing inequities at the intersection of sport, development, and education. Such an endeavour is focused on the promotion of inclusion and social justice through the application of theoretical frameworks that have sought to address inequity, the implementation of qualitative and participant centred methodologies and the value and complexity of transformational pedagogy. The aim will be addressed through the following objectives:

1. To critically reflect upon my personal, professional, political, and philosophical, experiences and perspectives in sport for development and education.
2. To synthesise and critically reflect upon the published articles in relation to participant engagement and outcomes, addressing inequity, inclusive practice for social justice and transformational pedagogy.
3. Summarise the key findings from the critical reflections and present future directions for scholarship at the intersection of sport, development, and education.

To achieve the aim and objectives, Chapter 2 analyses my research journey up to this point and is presented in two sections. Section 1 reflects on my experiences in SfD and education. My personal and professional experiences are explored in relation to how they have influenced, and been influenced by, my political position. Building upon this discussion section 2 reflects upon the philosophical perspectives adopted within the published articles. This is approached through critical and reflective discussions on ontology, epistemology, and methodology.

Section 2 also explores my positionality regarding research in education and SfD, with a particular focus on cultural sensitivity, and how this has influenced the geographical, social, cultural, and political complexities within the published articles.

Following this analysis, Chapter 3 critically reflects upon the contribution of the published articles by synthesising them into a coherent body of knowledge. The thematic analysis is supported through critical engagement with relevant literature from across SfD, development, education, and physical education scholarship.

Following the synthesis of the submitted articles, Chapter 4 discusses how the published articles have contributed to knowledge, reflects on what I have learned throughout the process, explores how that learning could be applied in future practice and/or scholarship and identifies future directions for my own research within the four thematic areas.

Having introduced the subject, the published articles, and the structure of the critical appraisal I will now address objective 1 through reflecting on my personal and professional experiences and my political and philosophical perspectives.

Chapter 2- Personal, Professional, Political and Philosophical Reflections

The analysis of my research journey is outlined in two sections. In section 1 I reflect upon my personal and professional experiences, and my political perspectives. The section focuses on how these experiences and perspectives have influenced my position on education, SfD and politics. This position is underpinned by the ambition of addressing inequity through incorporating my perspectives on inclusion, transformational pedagogy, the relationship between luck and structural inequality, and the realisation of positive social change. It is the understanding and knowledge that I have gained from these perspectives that have informed and continue to develop my research philosophy.

In section 2 I reflect upon the philosophical assumptions that have informed my work. As Grix (2002) states the intention is to present a clear and transparent picture of the ontological and epistemological assumptions and my positionality within them. My epistemological, ontological, and methodological assumptions have formed my thinking about and understanding of the world. They have also influenced my perspectives of critical, collaborative, and qualitative research and the overarching approach adopted within the published articles. These are presented in Table 2.

Table 2 – Research Strategies & Paradigms

Strategy	Abductive
Ontology	Idealist
Epistemology	Constructivism
Research Paradigm	Interpretivism
Methodology	Critical Qualitative

Blaikie (2010) identified that any research strategy entails a particular combination of ontological and epistemological assumptions and provides the starting point for answering what and why questions. In response to this perspective, I have employed an abductive research strategy throughout the published articles to answer what and why questions. This has been undertaken through incorporating the meanings, interpretations, motives, and intentions that people use in their everyday lives. An abductive strategy enabled the social world of the research participants, and me as the researcher, to be explored as it was perceived and experienced. My aim was to discover '*why people do what they do by uncovering the largely tacit, mutual knowledge, the symbolic meanings, intentions, and rules, which provide the orientation for their actions*' (Blaikie, 2010, p.89).

The intention was to present descriptions and understandings that reflect the point of view of participants rather than presenting a top-down perspective solely from the point of view of the researcher. The adoption of an abductive research strategy links directly to the adoption of specific ontological, epistemological, and paradigmatic assumptions.

In adopting an idealist ontology in my published research, I have been concerned with how I understand and articulate beliefs about the nature of reality, what can be known about it and how I would go about attaining this knowledge. It is my understanding that reality is seen through people's beliefs and perceptions. Knowledge is a social construct with meanings explored in different ways, by different people in different contexts. Adhering to an idealist ontology has guided me towards a constructivist epistemology. Through individual constructions people perceive, interpret, experience, and explain the same phenomenon in a different way. I, therefore, view knowledge as personal, subjective, and unique. This is about understanding how individuals interpret the social phenomena they interact with and how knowledge is created through perceptions and interpretations of the world. Truth and reality are created, not discovered (Rehman & Alharthi, 2016).

My intentions to discover truth and reality ensured that the methodological approaches that I have employed have been predominantly qualitative and critical in nature. Qualitative research enables the interpretation of the diversity and lived experiences of participants. Complex interactions of power and socio-cultural difference can be transcended through collaboration and partnership. This enables the adoption of a critical lens that seeks to directly challenge the workings of power. It is my belief that the role of a critical qualitative researcher is to critique those in positions of power and expose the oppressive structures that create inequity. In order to reflect in greater depth on my research philosophy I will explore ontology, epistemology, and methodology further in section 2.2.

This research approach has required me to reflect critically upon my own positionality. My opinions, values, beliefs, and social background accompany me through the research process, shaping the decisions that I make. Our biases shape the research process and through recognition of those biases, insights are gained into how to engage with participants (Bourke, 2014). In these circumstances questions of power, privilege, and position are essential to ensure appropriate representation of participants and to continuously reflect upon the impact of my positionality on those participants (Vanner, 2015). Positionality is a continuous and reflexive process on the part of the researcher. Being reflexive ensures that my positionality continues to evolve in a culturally sensitive way, shaping my understanding of the world and the people with whom I interact (Bourke, 2014). In section 2.1.3 I will further explore my positionality in relation to my political perspectives.

2.1 Reflection 1: Personal, professional, and political reflections

2.1.1 Reflections on Education

In 1998 I worked at a school in Zimbabwe for six months. This opportunity provided me with my first experience of working in education as well as living and working in a completely

different environment. After returning from Africa and further travels in Brazil, I completed my degree in 2001. Following my degree, I was employed at a training organisation in East London where I worked with young people who had been excluded from school on a life skills programme. The role provided me with direct experience of how inequity impacts upon young people's life chances and reinforced my ambition to pursue a career in education.

Following completion of my Postgraduate Certificate in Education in 2004, I became a lecturer in sport at a further and higher education college in Blackburn. The college had, over several years, developed an inclusive approach through ensuring all learners were taught together in mainstream classes regardless of their disability and/or learning difficulty. For the first nine years I was employed in further education managing the provision of sport at Level 1 (pre-GCSE Level). Over time, and through working in collaboration with the learning support team, the programme embraced inclusive practices and created positive outcomes for students from highly challenging backgrounds. It was during this time that I completed a part time MEd in Inclusive Education at the University of Manchester. For the remaining five years at the college, I performed a variety of different roles in higher education including mentoring PGCE students, lecturing on the BA Hons in Education Studies and as course leader for BSc Community Coaching and Sport Development.

The transition from further to higher education was driven by an increased opportunity to work with professionals in education and sport and to undertake academic research. My enthusiasm and interest in education was influenced by the experience of working with vulnerable young people for over 10 years. By building on my professional experience and my MEd, I undertook research that developed my understanding of, and explored potential solutions for, inequity in both education and sport.

My approach to teaching in FE/HE and in my current role as a lecturer in sport at the University of the West of Scotland has been influenced by the work of Paulo Freire and his pedagogical approach to social, political, and educational transformation. Transformative learning is a deep learning experience and is defined by participation in constructive discourse that enables people to share their experiences and to use the experiences of others to develop their understanding of their own views, opinions, and assumptions and how these are influenced (Brown, 2014). As established in SES (2022) this is achieved through dialogue that is in accordance with the experiences of people rather than in direct contrast to it. Dialogue establishes a situation of trust that is reinforced by the concrete intentions from one party to another (Freire, 1972). The promotion of dialogical action within my practice enables me to facilitate sessions that provide the opportunity for students to explore their own personal situation objectively, developing their understanding of the different levels of their existence and how they perceive the world in which they exist (Freire, 1972). My understanding, and application, of critical pedagogy within my teaching practice has also enabled me to transfer those principles into my work and scholarship in SfD and physical education.

In acknowledging my own good fortune outlined in the above reflection, I believe that luck is a significant determinant in life. Luck enables the exploration of how much credit or blame we deserve for what we achieve. A lucky occurrence is one that involves chance, is consequential and partially outside the control of the person or people affected by it. Lack of control is a defining characteristic of luck and involves consequential events and an outcome that is at least partially due to chance. Luck, in effect, is chance with consequences (Sauder, 2020).

My understanding of luck and how privilege can impact other people, both positively and negatively, has been influenced by John Rawls' *A Theory of Justice*. The key element of the theory is that to provide genuine equity of opportunity society must give more attention to those with fewer native assets and to those born into less favourable social positions. If one person

is worse off than another through no fault or choice of their own, the situation is unfair, and hence *'inequality between the two people is objectionable'* (Munoz–Darde, 2014, p.473). Whether a society is just or unjust depends on the way that individuals and institutions deal with this situation (Rawls, 1971). For privileged individuals, both within and outwith institutions, acknowledging their own fortune increases their understanding of, and empathy for, others misfortune, the circumstances in which they exist and the structural factors which reinforce inequity.

Luck is however, difficult to measure and can be overlooked when we are unable to account for it. These limitations can lead to misattributing outcomes to luck when they are caused by hidden structural patterns (Sauder, 2020). The distribution of luck in society, is not happenstance, but *systematic* (Dowding,1996). As Sauder (2020) states the recognition of luck offers an accurate and comprehensive depiction of stratification processes that impact upon our understanding of the origins of and contributors to unequal outcomes. Recognizing the role luck plays in individual outcomes is a counter point to dogmatic beliefs of meritocracy. Luck is real, consequential, and significant. A failure to recognise the role that luck plays in our lives makes us less likely to contribute to the infrastructures and environments that provided us with the opportunities to be successful, through having the chance to be lucky, in the first place (Frank, 2016).

Luck and its influence on how people view the world and their position within it has impacted my view of inequity within society and how it could potentially be addressed. I believe that once individuals can accept that their privilege is based on luck more than judgement, hard work or social awareness the greater likelihood is that they would accept the principles of distributive justice (Rawls, 1971). This is about critically exploring the relationship between individual awareness and structural reform, and it is this perspective that continues to inform my understanding of inequity in educational practice and scholarship.

2.1.2 Reflections on Sport for Development

My published articles with SfD have focused on both the global North (IRSS, 2019) and the global South (JSFD, 2017; SES, 2022). In reflecting on SfD in a global North context, specifically in relation to community cohesion, I consider sport in its broadest sense to be a political project. It is a site of dynamic interplay of asserting and generating loci for change (Watson et al, 2013). Sport based interventions are viewed as a way to alleviate the distorted relations that exist between people and the agencies who engage with them (Haudenhuyse et al, 2012). The UK Government highlighted that sport has inherent qualities that enable it to play a role in building more cohesive, empowered, and active communities (Department of Culture, Media & Sport, 2008). Sport can be used as a tool to intervene within complex societies and to promote a greater level of mutual understanding on a grassroots level between different cultural groups within a specific community (Sugden & Haasner, 2009). The rules that govern sport are not based on faith or belief systems, therefore participation in sport or recreation easily opens itself to creating links between people from different cultures, countries, and backgrounds (European Commission, 2009).

The belief is that sport, through its inherent values has the capacity to contribute towards wider social objectives. This is achieved by building interventions that enhance community engagement and development (Bolton et al, 2008) and improving, in some small way, the wellbeing of a community (Jarvie, 2005). At the heart of this is the ethos of community empowerment that develops the autonomous capacity for communities to do things for themselves (Partington & Totten, 2012). The greater the level of community participation that exists the greater the likelihood is that participants will develop an attachment and engage with the ideas and solutions to resolve the issues that affect their daily lives (Glover, 2004).

The increased recognition that sport can be used in a way that contributes to the social fabric of societies with the perceived power to create positive change does not go unchallenged (Giulianotti, 2004). Contrary to the notion of sport as a salve for the rot of a fractured and fracturing society, it may ironically produce the very opposite in outcome of the purpose for which it was originally intended (Garratt, 2010). The competitive and traditionally exclusive elements of sport are in direct contrast to sports ability to work as a social agent of change. Sport can exacerbate difference rather than overcome it, reinforcing group boundaries and intergroup relationships rather than breaking them down. Rather than ask how sport can contribute to social cohesion, we should consider how sport can help negotiate the inevitability of cultural conflict and difference (Hutchins, 2007).

There is therefore, a need to focus on how sport can be used to address wider social issues whilst being fully aware of how poorly designed interventions reinforce the very issue they are seeking to resolve. Awareness is essential in understanding the impact of inflated promises and the lack of conceptual clarity (Coalter, 2011). Sport is not homogenous and therefore as a stand-alone entity is not transformative. Implementing a sport programme in any specific community is complex as intended outcomes are not easily measurable. It is intangible as it is both hard to define and to value. Benefits are not always obvious to see in the short term (Jones & Stokes, 2003). It is wrong to assume for instance, that something which works in a specific community can be easily transported and reassembled to work in a community with vastly different social and political histories (Stidder & Sugden, 2003). Alternative approaches require investigation to develop an ideological perspective that relates directly to resolving specific issues within specific communities through sport. Therefore in order for social change to occur through sport an awareness of its limitations is essential.

In considering both its strengths and its weaknesses I contend that sport does have the potential to advance various dimensions for development if used effectively and productively in

collaboration with the broader development sector. In the context of the global South sport has the capacity to reach groups which have been a challenge for development agencies in the past and to enhance existing development categories such as education (Darnell, 2007; Levermore, 2008; Black, 2009; Coalter, 2010; Guest, 2009; Jarvie, 2011; Kidd, 2008; Levermore, 2011 & Burnett, 2009). Education is at the heart of a significant number of SfD programmes, yet education policy within SfD is not always communicated, understood, or implemented in the way that it is intended (Schulenkorf et al, 2016). Adequate attention has not been given to pedagogical practice within SfD, especially considering how central it is for many programmes (Spaaij & Jeanes, 2013). This is particularly problematic within the representation of different histories and perspectives (Rossi & Jeanes, 2016; Darnell, 2014; Mwaanga & Banda 2014 & Mwaanga & Adeosun 2017).

These concerns are reflected through curriculum design within SfD. In a significant number of projects curriculum is developed in the global North and implemented in the global South. Education is delivered through manuals and practices that reinforce an unequal relationship regarding knowledge, and the way in which that knowledge is applied in practice (McSweeney et al, 2019). The concern is that SfD organisations have failed to deliver development through education, and this raises the question of why individuals/ communities / organisations / governments within the global South would buy into projects that fail to deliver development for them? (Mwaanga & Adeosun, 2019)

These concerns resonate with my own experience of designing and delivering a SfD project in Cape Town, South Africa. It was a very challenging experience and one that ultimately failed to fully deliver on its intended objectives for several reasons both within and outside of my control. The key issue during the development of the organisation and in the subsequent article written about the experience (JSFD, 2017) was how both the pedagogical and methodological approach failed to connect with the transformational aim and objectives of the project.

Reinforcing a hegemony framework through traditional research approaches raised the question of whose interests were being served through dominant ideas, in which contexts and with what effects (Darnell & Hayhurst, 2012).

From the experience of designing and delivering a SfD project, I wanted to explore methodological and pedagogical approaches utilised within SfD, their impact on participants and their capacity to deliver on their social change objectives. To enhance my understanding further I have explored participatory methodologies in IRSS (2019) and transformational pedagogy in SES (2022). This has enabled me to develop a more in depth understanding of the challenges, complexities, and benefits of participatory and transformational approaches within SfD. From my perspective, SfD has a significant role to play in facilitating social change but only when its educational focus incorporates the principle of equity and is developed through collaboration with local stakeholders and participants.

2.1.3 Political reflections

I believe at this stage it is important to lay out my political position as this is relevant to theories employed within the published articles. I have previously discussed two conflicting political perspectives which have influenced my life and professional practice. Rawls's *A Theory of Justice* sits within the liberal tradition and Freire's critical pedagogy is based upon Marxism and its expansion into critical theory. Whilst influenced by both perspectives, I consider myself neither a liberal nor a Marxist. I do not want to define my political perspectives within a singular school of thought. Adopting a rigid ideological position removes the opportunity to explore the variety of perspectives that are available to realise social change. Much of our current social and political issues are due to binary positions being adopted, but social and political issues are more fluid, nuanced and complex than any single ideological perspective can address. It is my view that addressing social and political issues, including education and

sport, is most likely to be achieved through incremental change. I acknowledge the potential naivety in my position, but to achieve social change there is a requirement to influence stakeholders progressively and incrementally. An example of this is in attempting to implement critical pedagogy in either education or SfD.

The potential for SfD or physical education to contribute to the making of critical citizens and liberal democratic ideals must be kept in perspective. Tinning (2017) states that when critical pedagogy is used in a way that challenges people it can create a feeling of confusion within the individual. It is expecting them to question much of what they know and that they have learned through the reality of their lives. This is uncomfortable and not without significant challenge as it involves questioning one's own place in social and political hierarchies, to displace one's own power (Fitzpatrick, 2019). Regarding this perspective, I agree with Shelly & McCuaig (2019) that people may well be able to acknowledge their privilege even if they are not necessarily able to explore the problematic implications that this raises.

With these issues in mind, addressing iniquities in SfD requires people to engage with ideas for participant engagement, social justice, inclusion, and transformative pedagogy. In this context language is fundamental. Describing SfD practitioners as oppressors, for example, when they see themselves as working hard to bring positive change to people's lives means that they are highly unlikely to engage with the challenges and complexities within those ideas. This position does not dismiss the existence of oppression in SfD. If oppression was not prevalent then inequity would not be such a significant issue. Rather it acknowledges oppressive practices whilst understanding that to change those practices it is fundamental that practitioners understand the value in these approaches to education within SfD projects, the importance of their position within them and their role in facilitating social change.

This requires the understanding that oppression is not always deliberate. There is a lack of understanding in those who seek to liberate in how to apply the principles of critical pedagogy. They themselves are surrounded and influenced by the environment that has created the oppression and are usually a product of that oppression. They are unaware of their role in reinforcing this oppression and its power to dehumanize (Freire, 1972). Paradoxically, many people who are intending to liberate through education are utilizing the same *'instrument of alienation in what they consider an effort to liberate'* (Freire, 1972, p.79). This reinforces Western ways of seeing and knowing which can lead to the undervaluing of other knowledge systems and maintain the unequal relationships through dialogue and power (Andretti and De Souza, 2008). This can be overcome through engagement with praxis, which is defined as the capacity to reflect and act upon the world in order that it can be transformed (Freire, 1972). The fundamental concept of praxis will be discussed in further detail in section 3.1.3 as part of a critical and reflective synthesis of the published articles exploration of transformational pedagogy.

To increase the likelihood that politicians, policy makers and/or practitioners engage with these ideas through praxis, the intention should be to work incrementally and to aim for partial change. This is known as ritual appropriation, where new practices are accepted and incorporated within the old. Practice is redefined to ensure continuity despite those changes. There is a clear connection between the old and the new, they are separate, but they mutually affect one another (Todd, 2004). An increased understanding of social change and its connection with ritual appropriation would significantly influence the design, implementation, and realisation of intended social change outcomes in SfD. In turn, this would enable SfD scholars to analyse social, political, economic, and historical factors that impact upon the realisation of ritual appropriation. Such an analysis would directly address the wider socio-political factors that impact upon people's lives. This is the process of achieving positive social

change and it is this position that influences the political, social, and educational intentions of my research philosophy.

Having reflected upon my personal, professional and political experiences/perspectives I will now discuss my philosophical position in relation to the published articles. The intention is to discuss how this position has developed over time and to reflect upon my ontological, epistemological, methodological position and how this has impacted upon my cultural understanding and positionality.

2.2 Reflection 2: Philosophical Reflections

2.2.1 Ontological reflections

In adopting the ontological assumption of an idealist, I believe that reality consists of representations that are the creation of the human mind. An idealist assumption explores how the social reality of participants is made up of shared interpretations that are produced and re-produced as people experience their everyday lives. The idealist assumption is constructivist and adopts the position that constructions of reality are regarded as different perspectives on an external world (Blaikie, 2010).

Complexities in an idealist ontology are highlighted when the experiences or perceptions of the research participants are not fully realised and are driven from the reality of the researcher as opposed to the lived reality of the participants. In developing my knowledge and understanding of the research process in IRSS (2019) for example, I have been able to both reflect upon and seek to address these flaws. An increased awareness of how to apply an idealist ontology enabled a more critical appraisal of how individuals, through interaction, connect their lived experiences to the cultural representations of those experiences. This approach facilitates the opportunity for explicit engagement in cultural criticism. In this context, cultural

criticism informs the use of a constructivist epistemology with the belief that people effectively construct knowledge and meaning through the reality that surrounds them (Denzin, 2002).

2.2.2 Epistemological reflections

Through a constructivist epistemology, both I as the researcher and the participants within the research brought our own personal experiences and opinions to the table. A constructivist epistemology is both transactional and subjectivist. It is rooted in critical theory through the interactive linking of the researcher and the objects of investigation. In SES (2022) for example I was able to explore the connection between critical theory and constructivism which enabled me to explore the subject matter through an increased understanding of the broader social, political, and cultural structures that inevitably impact upon the research (Guba & Lincoln, 2005).

Through a constructivist epistemology in RPCE (2018) and IJSP (2020) I was able to explore specific phenomena critically and politically. Within the process, I understood the requirement to reduce bias and ensure validity within the representation of data from a political perspective. It is however, difficult to separate ourselves from what we know and what we believe. Our subjectivity is an integral part of our understanding of ourselves, of others and of the world around us (Angen, 2000). In JSFD (2017) it was important to be aware that subjectivity was in turn derived from the history and culture of the communities in which I and the participants were from. This requires undertaking the role both facilitator and participant, such as in IRSS (2019). In this role, I aimed for consensus whilst being open to new interpretations through dialogue, as the process evolved (Carr & Kemmis, 1986). The nature of knowledge within a constructivist epistemology is based upon individual reconstructions that coalesce around consensus. In this context I concur with Guba and Lincoln (2005) in that knowledge is

accumulated through informed and sophisticated reconstructions that are based upon vicarious experiences.

2.2.3 Paradigmatic Reflections

In adopting interpretive enquiry my intention was to go beyond the research of isolated issues and enable an in-depth study of contextual and complex issues. My aim was to understand the complexities of specific phenomena through lived experiences and the points of view from participants who have lived that experience (Schwandt, 1998). Adopting an interpretivist approach to data capture through methods such as semi-structured interviews (JSFD, 2017; IRSS, 2019); IJSP, 2020) and auto-ethnography (RPCE, 2018) allowed me to critically explore the complex realities that people face in their day to day lives. This enabled interpretive explorations of highly complex social and political issues such as social cohesion, social justice, inclusive practice, and critical pedagogy. In exploring such complex issues within an interpretivist paradigm, I was able to interpret how meaning was constructed by participants and clarify how that meaning was embodied into the actions of social actors (Schwandt, 1998). This approach enabled the exploration of how knowledge is constructed from within the mind of an individual. Knowledge does not exist outside of those who create and hold those constructions (Guba & Lincoln, 2005).

2.2.4 Methodological reflections

Within the published articles I have employed a variety of qualitative or predominantly qualitative methodologies as they are exploratory in nature and concerned with how the social world is interpreted, understood, experienced, or produced (Molina-Azorin, 2007). Through these methodological approaches the intention was to make sense of situations without imposing pre-existing expectations and perceptions (Dasgupta, 2015), and to produce rounded understandings based on rich, contextual, and detailed data (Mason, 1996).

My initial understanding of methodology derived from my awareness of case study research from an educational perspective. Numerous studies across education and sport have utilised a variety of case study approaches, including single, multiple, and intrinsic case study. They can employ a variety of methods across quantitative and qualitative approaches. For JSFD (2017) I employed a critical qualitative case study. The approach was adopted as it informs education through a lens that ensures the investigation of issues in education tied to power and privilege (White, 2015). Case study research is qualitative and closely aligned with a constructivist and interpretivist orientation and underpinned by a strong motivation for discovering meaning and understanding of experiences in context (Harrison et al, 2017). A case is specific, complex, and functioning. It has a boundary and working parts that draws us towards observing the problems of the case and the complex backgrounds of human concern (Stake, 1995). Through undertaking a case study in JSFD (2017) my role was to capture the interpreted reality of participants within the case alongside studying the case simultaneously. This enabled an examination of the integrated system in which the case unfolded (Harrison et al, 2017). This was reinforced through the understanding that the project and the individuals and organisations responsible for its development and possible implementation were essentially a bounded entity that could not be removed from contextual conditions (Stake, 2008).

In continuing with a case study methodology IJSP (2020) adopted a mixed method case study to develop further understanding as to the rationale for how schools are spending their PESP funding. The method employed combined the case study approaches in two separate quantitative and qualitative case studies undertaken by Griggs (2016; 2018) which analysed how primary schools were spending their PESP in the West Midlands. Applying a mix of both qualitative and quantitative methods offered creative possibilities for addressing the aim of the research without being tied down to a particular philosophical position (Brannen 2005). The process focused on understanding a particular phenomenon in order to provide an analysis that

is informed by multiple and diverse perspectives, strengthening the inferences that can be made from across the data (Sammons et al. 2005). The approach follows Hammersley (2002) by ensuring that the political currency accorded to a practical enquiry is highly relevant to policy, policymakers, and practice.

RPCE (2018) also utilised a mixed method approach, initially undertaking auto-ethnography before a series of interviews that further explored the initial findings of the auto-ethnography in greater depth. This approach was influenced by the work of Forde (2015) from an SfD perspective and Trahar (2013) from an educational perspective. Through auto-ethnography data was presented through the production of co-authored, co-constructed and collaborative texts. Responses were edited and intertwined with my own autoethnography to create a cohesive and collaborative narrative that told the story of the course and the college. It involved the sharing of unique, subjective, and evocative stories of experience that contribute to our understanding of our world and enable a reflexive approach to learning (Wall, 2008). It was my own and others creative construction of reality, which we lived through. It was a view of reality constructed around and through others (Dyson, 2005). There was an awareness of the subjectivity of the story being told. Stories are altered through fallible memories and the representation of perceived reality. Auto-ethnography requires an awareness that all participants within the research do not recall, remember, or interpret in the same way significant events or actions. Significant variations exist within participants in similar positions with similar experiences. The way in which people interpret events or understand cultural realities are often highly variable, changing, or contradictory (Hayano, 1979). Auto-ethnography is not only deeply personal and self-observant it also address collectively, broader theoretical issues within an analytical tradition. It is an analytical rather than evocative methodology.

In IRSS (2019) PAR was chosen to promote engagement from participants and to gain their understanding of the role that sport could play in resolving the issue of cultural separation. My approach to PAR was influenced by studies by Hayhurst et al, 2016; Spaaij et al, 2017 and Mwaanga & Adeosun, 2017. I utilised PAR as it encourages capacity building and development in all who participate (McTaggart, 1997) promoting community involvement and giving people a voice. PAR has been applied within SfD to promote higher levels of interaction and engagement. For PAR to be undertaken successfully the interaction between researcher and participant is imperative if social change and empowerment are to occur (Selener, 1997). The desire for increased empowerment through this approach is however, tempered by the realisation that the promotion of empowerment is an on-going process of continuous struggle (Partington & Totten, 2012). Our understanding of reality is constantly evolving, and the philosophical underpinning of PAR is more suited to understanding this shifting dynamic. It is a liberating methodology that maintains a commitment to local contexts (Marshall and Rossman, 2006) and ensures a reshaping of knowledge for both researcher and participants as to how political, social, economic, and familial contexts within communities impact daily life (McIntyre, 2002).

Moving beyond primary data capture SES (2022) employed a qualitative systematic review with the intention to develop a holistic interpretation of the phenomenon through a selective search approach. A qualitative systematic review is a method for comparing the findings from qualitative studies (Grant & Booth ,2009). It involves a systematic search process to locate studies which address a particular research question, as well as a systematic presentation and synthesis of the characteristics and findings of the results of this search. The approach was influenced by systematic literature review undertaken by McSweeney & Nakamura (2019). This was adapted to focus specifically on qualitative studies to maintain my qualitative approach to scholarship and to ensure that finding were based on the lived experiences of

research participants. The rationale for applying a qualitative systematic review in SES (2022) is that it is able to address broader questions than single empirical studies can (Baumeister & Leary, 1997). The intention was to accumulate knowledge through the development of an overarching narrative, a wider generalisation, or an interpretative translation.

In the planning and undertaking of primary data capture throughout the published articles, consultations and conversations were facilitated with different stakeholders. This was both flexible and dynamic. The process constantly evolved and adapted through reflections on the knowledge being gained. This flexible process was particularly relevant considering the state of flux regarding the SfD project in JSFD (2017), inclusive practice in the college (RPCE, 2018), community relations in IRSS (2019), and policy enactment in IJSP (2020). Specific descriptions of the nature and number of participants, the process of ethics applications and the procedural issues of the process are highlighted in table 3.

Table 3: Methods, Participants & Procedures

Journal Article	Research Participants & Data Capture	Ethics procedure	Documentation
JSFD (2017)	<p>Data capture was undertaken through questionnaires, focus group and individual interviews across two cohort groups.</p> <p>Total questionnaires undertaken = 45</p> <p>Total Focus Groups undertaken = 8 (27 participants)</p> <p>Total individual interviews undertaken = 3</p>	<p>An ethics application was submitted to, and approved by, the ethics review panel at University Centre Blackburn College.</p>	<p>All participants were provided with the following documents for their agreement prior to participation in the research:</p> <p>Participant information sheet</p> <p>Informed consent form</p> <p>A risk assessment was undertaken at three different sites</p>

			prior to the data capture being undertaken.
RPCE (2018)	<p>Data capture was undertaken through individual responses to a series of set questions. These responses to part 1 of the data capture were undertaken by 3 Lecturers, 2 Curriculum Support Co-ordinators, 4 Additional Learning Support Workers, and 1 Curriculum Area Manager. These responses were combined with my own to create an auto-ethnography. Total participants who contributed to the auto-ethnography = 10</p> <p>Stage 2 of data capture involved 1-1 interviews with the Curriculum Area Manager for Sport and the manager of Additional Learning Support. s focus group were undertaken with the current course team for Level 1 Sport programme including one course leader and two lecturers, three Curriculum Centre Support Coordinators and two Additional Learning Support Workers. Total participants who contributed to stage 2 of data capture = 8</p>	<p>An ethics application was submitted to, and approved by, the ethics review panel at University Centre Blackburn College.</p> <p>Further reviews were undertaken of the application by senior college leaders prior to the research commencing.</p>	<p>All participants were provided with the following documents for their agreement prior to participation in the research:</p> <p>Participant information sheet</p> <p>Informed consent form</p> <p>A risk assessment was already in place due to the data capture being undertaken at my place of work.</p>
IRSS (2019)	<p>Stage 1 data capture: Recorded group discussion with research participants from a local further education college and a local youth centre. Seven focus groups were undertaken. Total number of participants = 28 (22 boys & 6 girls aged 15-19).</p> <p>Stage 2 data capture: Four focus groups with research participants. Total number of participants = 10 (7 boys & 3 girls aged 15-19).</p> <p>Stage 3 data capture: Three interviews. One with two youth work</p>	<p>An ethics application was submitted to, and approved by, the ethics review panel at University Centre Blackburn College.</p>	<p>All participants were provided with the following documents for their agreement prior to participation in the research:</p> <p>Participant information sheet</p>

	managers, another with an individual youth worker and one focus group with three young participants (2 boys aged 17 and 19 and one girl aged 16).		<p>Informed consent form for participants</p> <p>Informed consent form for parents of participants under the age of 16.</p> <p>A risk assessment was undertaken at two different sites prior to the data capture being undertaken.</p>
IJSPP (2020)	<p>Stage 1 data capture: Quantitative analysis of PESP data from 46 primary school websites.</p> <p>Stage 2 data capture: Analysis of written statements on school websites; 1-1 interviews with four Physical Education Subject Leaders; 1-1 interview with the School Games Organiser; 1-1 interview with the Relationship Manager for the County Sport Partnership. Total number of research participants = 6</p>	An ethics application was submitted to, and approved by, the ethics review panel at University Centre Blackburn College.	<p>All participants were provided with the following documents for their agreement prior to participation in the research:</p> <p>Participant information sheet</p> <p>Informed consent form for participants</p> <p>A risk assessment was undertaken at five different sites prior to interviews.</p>

Throughout the published articles the primary method of data capture was interviews. Individual Interviews were utilised within the published articles to obtain the perspectives, feelings, and perceptions from the participants (Holloway, 1997). The intention was to engage in a conversation in a semi structured way with the participants to jointly construct knowledge about themselves and the social world. Semi structured interviews provide a clear set of

questions to allow for parity across the different interview participants whilst allowing for a level of flexibility for the participants to express their ideas, feelings, and attitudes. The intention was to provide a deeper knowledge and understanding than would have emerged from a structured process (Sparkes & Smith, 2014).

Alongside 1-1- interviews primary data capture within the published articles involved undertaking a series of focus group interviews with a variety of stakeholders, participants, and practitioners. Focus group interviews involve several people collaboratively sharing ideas, feelings, thoughts and perceptions about a certain topic and specific issues within that topic area. My role was as a facilitator with the intention of creating a supportive atmosphere for the expression of personal, multiple and on occasion conflicting viewpoints and perspectives (Sparkes & Smith, 2014). Focus group interviews were undertaken using an alternative constructionist approach to access various stories or narratives through which people describe their world (Riessman, 2008). Interviews throughout the research process in IRSS (2019) were directly related to the participatory nature of the research. This provided participants with a high degree of control over the direction and content of the discussions and opened up the possibility to generate plausible accounts of the world through the pursuit of a different, narrated reality in which locally produced narratives are to the fore (Silverman, 2017). It was essential to ensure that participants were provided with the opportunity to engage with the process on an equal basis and to have the opportunity to influence the process itself.

Due to the qualitative approach employed within my research thematic analysis was employed in the analysis of data throughout the published articles. Thematic analysis is a useful method for examining the perspectives of different research participants and generating unanticipated insights (Nowell et al, 2017). Thematic analysis is also an appropriate form of analysis for producing qualitative data that is well suited to informing policy development (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Data analysis is the most complex phase of qualitative research and to ensure

trustworthiness through the process of thematic analysis, it was fundamental to demonstrate how the analysis was conducted in a precise, consistent, and exhaustive manner through recording, systemising, and disclosing the methods of analysis (Thorne, 2000).

Themes were defined through emerging patterns from within all corresponding data. This process provided the opportunity to delve deeper into the meaning of the texts and to identify the patterns that underlie the themes (Attride-Stirling, 2001). Following this process, the themes were revised and reviewed in seeking to form a coherent pattern (Nowell et al, 2017). It was also important to ensure the validity of the themes to ensure that they accurately reflected the meanings that were evident in the data as a whole (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Significant time was invested throughout the thematic analysis of each article to increase the probability of developing credible findings (Lincoln & Guba, 1985).

Whilst the approaches undertaken were qualitative, it was also important that the methodologies incorporated critical enquiry. The synthesis of a qualitative and critical approach is justified through an understanding of the complexity of the object of enquiry and the demands that such complexity places on the research process itself. The objects of enquiry were too complex to be *'viewed by a single way of seeing or as a snapshot of a particular phenomenon at a specific moment in time'* (Kincheloe et al, 2012, p.24). The core idea is to understand that knowledge is constructed by existing sets of social relations and therefore the aim of a qualitative and critical methodology is to engage with social structures and policy that are considered to be oppressive in nature (Sparkes & Smith, 2014). Critical qualitative research is a social theoretical act that is headlined by a socially just and equitable practice (Steinberg, 2012). The aspiration to be critical was an attempt to confront social injustice, to dig beneath the surface of historically specific, oppressive, social structures and to focus on moments of ideology, hegemony, and possible emancipation (Sparkes & Smith, 2014).

It is important at this stage to state that my critical and qualitative perspective was not fully formed as I started to undertake academic research. My engagement with critical qualitative enquiry has been a developmental and reflective process over the last six years. The process has been influenced by the work of Denzin (2017) who developed five points for how critical qualitative enquiry contributes towards social justice. These five points have incrementally influenced the way in which I have approached critical and qualitative research within the published articles. First, critical qualitative enquiry helps to identify different definitions of problems. Second, it can locate assumptions, often belied by the facts of experience, and show them to be correct or incorrect. Third, it can identify strategic points of intervention into social situations. Fourth, it is possible to suggest that programmes must always be judged by and from the point of view of the persons most directly affected. Fifth, it can expose the limits of statistical evaluation.

These points support the perspective that critical scholars are committed to showing how the practices of critical, interpretive, and qualitative research can change the world in a positive way (Denzin, 2017). The intention of seeking positive social change (through ritual appropriation) was the rationale for the progressive application of critical qualitative methodologies. To realise this ambition, it was fundamental to ensure that I engaged in a constant process of reflection. This reflection focused on the progressive development of culturally sensitive methodological approaches that were informed through an idealist ontology, a constructivist epistemology, and an interpretivist paradigm.

2.2.5 Navigating relationships and access

In terms of navigating relationships and access for the data capture in my published articles I will focus specifically on JSFD (2017) and IRSS (2019). These were the most complex

relationships and therefore provide a richer and more nuanced context for reflection and discussion.

Gaining and maintaining research access through specific individuals, referred to as gatekeepers or encultured informants is fundamental to the gaining of access and the development of rich and informed narratives. Gatekeepers are instrumental in shaping access and content and therefore have a significant influence the type and quality of the data collected (Collison et al, 2016). An appropriate example can be found in JSFD (2017) where the gatekeepers were two government departments in Cape Town with who we were working in partnership with to deliver the programmes. The partnership focused on implementation and delivery of programmes. This was a mutually beneficial partnership through the fact that the government departments provided access to facilities and participants whereas the Sfd organisation offered sport-based provision that complimented traditional curricula approaches and provided training to teachers to enable the sustainable development of sport within the school (Lindsey and Bello Bitugu, 2018). Whilst partnerships should be based upon the facilitation of collaborative work, disparity existed through differentiated power relations and patronage (Adams & Harris, 2014; Giulianotti et al, 2016; Lindsey & Bella-Bitugu, 2018). This situation was complicated by a variety of different stakeholder with different interests and aspirations.

Whilst there were complications in the different partnerships in JSFD (2017) access was granted without complications as data capture and post programme monitoring and evaluation were considered fundamental to the project as well as the government departments. A similar relationship was developed in IRSS (2019) between me as the researcher and the youth organisation. This was because the agreement regarding access to participants was fundamental the employment of PAR as the research methodology. The project would not have been able to start without an access agreement in place. The agreement was developed with the

understanding that participants became collaborators and contributors within the project. This was to ensure that participant knowledge would have value throughout the research process (Mwaanga & Adeosun, 2017). From my perspective in both JSFD (2017) and IRSS (2019) the intention was to create a mutually beneficial relationship between myself as the researcher and for the organisations who had sanctioned the research. It was important to build a trustful relationship with the community/project gatekeepers through the understanding that *'transparent, reciprocal and interactive relationships are based on the development of mutual trust and respect'* (Whitley & Johnson, 2015, p.630). There was a need to build the foundation of trust through shared experiences to gain truthful information from participants (Mwaanga & Adeosun, 2017).

In relation to trust and shared experiences I concur with Collison et al (2016) who state that the building of strong relationships between the researcher and local actors requires negotiation and exchange and is essential to the collection of accurate and valuable data. In IRSS (2019) specifically, this was about keeping the lines of communication open, being flexible to change once the programme was being delivered, sharing decision-making power and ownership and putting the needs of participants first to ensure that the work was *'truly reciprocal and collaborative'* (Spaaij et al, 2016, p.638). Ultimately however, it remains an inconvenient truth that without clearly defined processes of dissemination and engagement post research, the danger is that the researcher takes more (knowledge) from this mutually beneficial relationship than they give (Collison et al, 2016; Luguetti et al, 2022). In both JSFD (2017) and IRSS (2019) the research was more beneficial to me as the researcher than to the different partner organisations. This was not my intention but the breakdown in communication surrounding both data capture during the projects and afterwards regarding the monitoring and evaluation in JSFD (2017) created frictions in the relationships. Such outcomes highlight the complexities

of navigating relationships, ensuring lines of communication remain open, maintaining access within different cultural environment and in the undertaking of participatory research.

2.2.6 Cultural Reflections

The intention of a culturally sensitive approach to research is to transcend the complex interactions of power and socio-cultural difference that are encountered in multi-cultural sporting contexts (Schinke et al, 2013). I have made every effort to approach my research in a culturally sensitive way. This was to ensure that issues of ethnic division, disability, and social class, which were fundamental to the analysis within the published articles, as well as the views, perspectives, and experiences of the participants, were fairly represented. In approaching research in this way, I was required to critically assess my own cultural views and to ask the hard questions as to how those views may differ from the participants within the process. The awareness of cultural sensitivity within the research process extended to the impact of cultural views upon the choice of methods and required me to question '*who will be the beneficiaries of this knowledge and how will it help them*' (Schinke et al, 2013, p.208).

Cultural sensitivity has been fundamental in terms of working both across and within different communities and exploring complex issues of social class, social stratification, disability, and deprivation. This is particularly relevant considering my own white British identity, that I am able bodied, come from a middle-class background and have no personal experience of disability or deprivation and its impact on people's lives. Whilst it was the intention to approach research in a culturally sensitive way there have been wider and more complex issues which have created specific problems. In this context I concur with Collison et al (2016) who state that the building of strong relationships between researcher and local actors requires negotiation and exchange and is essential to the collection of accurate and valuable data. This

is the process of knowledge exchange and alongside requiring access, practical engagement and the creation of real-world impact is a fundamental methodological challenge.

In certain situations, the research process that I employed ignored or was unfamiliar with cultural protocol, and at times I fell into an *'intellectually arrogant trap'* (Aveling, 2013, p.206) of believing that as the researcher I knew what I was doing as well as what people needed (JSFD, 2017; IRSS, 2019). There was a lack of awareness of my own identity and positionality. Instead of focusing on perceived differences and shortcomings, I should have been reflective on the fact that my own ways of *'being, knowing and doing emanate from a position of white privilege, and are already historically and culturally specific'* (Aveling, 2013, p.210). In relation to this issue, Carr (2016) discusses the terms whiteness and white privilege. Whiteness is often rendered invisible through a process of normalisation and the influence of deeply entrenched dominant structures. Even when these concepts are addressed it does not mean that what is discussed or written about will be the reality of practice.

Whiteness has three inter-related components, these are a location of structural advantage, the standpoint from how those of us who are white understand the world and our position in it and a set of cultural practices that are dominant (Carr, 2016). Specifically within JSFD (2017) these components manifested themselves within the conflict between my awareness as a researcher, which was inevitably coloured by my own experiences alongside an awareness of the fact that there are other realities and worldviews other than my own. It was not possible for me to present clearly and coherently an absolute truth about experiences that I have not had. The reality is that as a researcher I am required to develop a more in-depth understanding of how my own whiteness and white privilege has influenced my research as *'it is essential that discussions, deliberations, and action plans be conceptualized and implemented to address, at myriad levels, white power, and privilege'* (Carr, 2016. p.69). It is therefore, essential that I continue

to reflect upon my own positionality in a culturally sensitive way and develop a clear structure for addressing inequities in the design, development, and analysis of SfD.

The above reflections on my personal, professional, political and research experiences have been presented with the intention of describing my development up to this point. The following section addresses objective 2 through a critical and reflective synthesise of the published articles into a coherent body of knowledge. The aim is to present the article's contribution and findings, and to explore how these relate to the broader literature across SfD and education.

Chapter 3. A Critical and Reflective Synthesis of the Published Articles

This chapter synthesises the published articles in a critical and reflective way. The synthesis analyses the theoretical frameworks, qualitative and participant centred methodologies and empirical findings from the articles in relation to the following four themes: (1) participant engagement and outcomes (2) addressing inequity (3) inclusion for social justice and (4) transformational pedagogy. See section 1.2 for description of how these themes were generated.

In section 3.1, participation engagement and outcomes are analysed through a synthesis of JSFD (2017) and IRSS (2019). The critical analysis of the methodological approach in JSFD (2017) focuses on the lack of participant engagement within the research process, the impact that this had on the intended project outcomes and my reflections on how these issues could have been resolved through a participatory approach.

In section 3.2, I explore how SfD can address inequity through a synthesis of IJSPP (2020), SES (2022) and JSFD (2017). Firstly, the section evaluates the challenges in defining equity. Secondly the value of Rawls Theory of Justice is discussed in the context of inequity in physical education policy through a social justice lens. Thirdly, equity is discussed within the context of SfD through a synthesis of empirical findings in JSFD (2017) and SES (2022).

In section 3.3 I synthesise RPCE (2018) and IJSPP (2020) to analyse how inclusive practice can be designed and implemented in collaboration with the principles of social justice. In the first instance I reflect upon my experiences as an inclusive educator and the empirical findings in RPCE (2018). Secondly, I explore social justice and its connection to inclusive practice. This is undertaken through an analysis of Rawls's Theory of Justice in IJSPP (2020). Finally, through incorporating findings from SES (2022) I discuss the ways in which inclusive practice and social justice can influence the development of transformational pedagogy in SfD.

In section 3.4 I synthesise findings from JSFD (2017) and SES (2022) to evaluate the rationale for, and challenges in, applying transformational pedagogy in SfD. The synthesis explores the flaws in the pedagogical approach adopted within the project in JSFD (2017) and how reflections on that process led to the development of a qualitative systematic review in SES (2022) that explored the possibilities of dialogical and critical pedagogy in SfD.

3.1 Participant Engagement and Outcomes

This section highlights the importance of (1) participant engagement (2) the complexity of designing and realising participant outcomes and (3) the importance of reflective practice in the realisation of participant engagement and outcomes. All three perspectives are relevant to the design, delivery, and analysis of SfD programmes. When these are undertaken in a collaborative way participants and other stakeholders are engaged and valued through a co-design process which engenders a sense of ownership. SfD scholarship should seek to actively involve research participants and demonstrate how it is rejecting or redressing the *'universal and top-down nature of experiences that are captured in contemporary scholarship, institutional policy and micro-level delivery'* (Banda & Holmes, 2017, p.13). In addressing this concern, I argue that *'the notion of co-production is fundamental for many community sport initiatives involving young people'* (IRSS, 2019, p.16). In analysing the importance of reflective practice, the section explores a developmental and evolving approach to participant engagement and the realisation of project outcomes.

3.1.1 Participant Engagement

JSFD (2017) was my first peer review publication. The article was an important first step for me in terms of academic research. During the review process the article was commended for its discussions on PAR and critical pedagogy, and this gave me the confidence and the reassurance to explore these concepts further in future articles. The focus on critical pedagogy

and PAR within the article has been significant in the development of my other articles on SfD. The article was particularly influential in the exploration of critical pedagogy in SES (2022) and the methodological approach utilised in IRSS (2019).

The closeness of the relationship between researchers, programmes, and participants can be *'identified as a major strength in trying to provide a nexus between theory, policy and the realities of practice'* (Schulenkorf, 2016, p.246). This position is enhanced further when there is an appropriate and relevant level of cultural engagement. A programme participant in the LETS project in Cape Town highlighted the requirement for continued cultural engagement in JSFD (2017, p.23) when they stated that:

The issues that LETS will face in trying to reach its aims is in the way in which it attempts to understand the culture in which it works and the backgrounds of the participants. It needs to research local issues and develop local based programmes.

This perspective reflects the importance of local knowledge and the understanding that all circumstances are unique and therefore all SfD programmes should be designed and delivered in a unique way. Such an approach would enable the concerns of the minority to be addressed with regard to equality, sustainability, and equitable partnerships (Burnett, 2015).

The methodological approach adopted within JSFD (2017) was not participatory. It did not include local voices in programme design and evaluation. On reflection I did not develop my understanding of my own privilege as well as my own limitations, biases, and partialities within the process (Spaaij et al, 2017). Due to the flaws of the research process within JSFD (2017) I advocated for participatory approaches to data capture within SfD. Such a process would have opened up spaces for alternative and critical perspectives and enabled a collaborative process through personal narratives that encouraged reflexivity. This would have created reciprocal engagement, rapport, and trust with stakeholders and participants (Sherry et al, 2017).

A more reflexive and collaborative approach can steer research in a politically and socially charged way through promoting alternative ways of seeing, knowing, and doing from the perspectives of the participants themselves (Hayhurst, 2017). Politically and social charged research can create a more critical, nuanced, and realistic appraisal that directly challenges the structural inequities that exist within sport. This can be achieved through embracing local knowledge and locally-driven research. On reflection, increased engagement and collaboration from programme partners involved in the delivery of the programmes discussed in JSFD (2017) would have addressed existent structural inequities between the project and the partner organisations and between the programme and the participants. Participatory methods can transcend the complex interactions of power and socio-cultural difference through equal collaboration and partnership. Participation enables people, through a philosophy of action, to determine their own development and to participate meaningfully in the process of finding their own solutions (Freire, 1972).

Further to this, I support the views of Darnell et al (2018) who advocate for participatory and first-person approaches to encourage reflexivity and collaboration to upend the research design process and to deconstruct the rhetoric, context, and narrative of SfD. To successfully apply PAR within SfD, Spaaij et al (2017) identify that participatory research should be conceptualized along three inter-related dimensions: the degree of local participation, the degree of power shifting and the degree of reflexivity. The degree of local participation refers to the extent to which those who are part of the research process are actively involved across all phases of the research. The initial methodological approach within JSFD (2017) did not conform to these three conceptualisations of participatory research. Local actors were engaged through a level of shallow participation. I controlled this process, and the participants were confined to taking part in the enquiries rather than being a driver in the research from the very beginning.

To address some of the concerns above and to further explore the possibilities of PAR as a research methodology I devised a project to address the issue of social cohesion. Whilst the original intention within IRSS (2019) was to address social cohesion within the borough of Blackburn in North West England, the most significant contribution of the article is methodological. The article was an open and honest account of the complexities of undertaking participatory research and it is this approach which resonated with scholars who are engaging with participatory approaches in sport. My recent invite to be a panel member on the *Doing PAR in Leisure Studies: Research design and navigating challenges* webinar provides evidence of the continued reach of the article.

The position adopted in IRSS (2019) was that

where sport matters in peoples' lives, it can lead to meaningful change. However, irrespective of its level of importance, change must be co-created, reciprocal, and participatory, involving young people from the design stage and then through delivery and evaluation (IRSS p.15).

This position reflects the importance of the process of participant engagement. Findings in IRSS (2019) highlighted that PAR positions local actors at the centre of the process, through enabling the co-construction and co-design of research projects. This approach contributed to a '*shift in power where local participants can come to own the research*' (Spaaij et al, 2017, p.7). A shift in power ensures that those who are directly affected by the issues concerned can resolve them independently and through consultation (IRSS, 2019).

Whilst PAR has the potential to engage with a variety of stakeholders and build trust, reciprocity and collaboration between research participants and communities, it is a challenging and complex methodology. This is due to the level of local community engagement required and the need to continually reflect and act upon ongoing processes (Sherry et al, 2017).

Criticism from participants involved within the research emphasised that it was overly prescriptive from the start and that they would have preferred to have greater autonomy over the focus of activities (IRSS, 2019). I accept the flaws evident within the process, there are however, significant benefits of using PAR to engender participant engagement. PAR promotes a more ethical approach to research that connects with the diversity and lived experiences of programme participants (Hayhurst, 2017) and encourages participants to take ownership of an initiative. It ensures that those who are directly affected by the issues concerned have the opportunity to resolve them independently and through consultation (IRSS, 2019).

In IRSS (2019) I argued that the adoption of participatory approaches to data capture is fundamental to providing the opportunity for social transformation. The methods employed are fundamental in ensuring appropriate and specific opportunities for ownership and engagement. This is because appropriate choices of data capture methods facilitate a progressive shift away from external change agents to local communities (Schulenkorf, 2016). Such an approach builds on the perspectives and experiences of those involved at the grassroots, creating a greater level of engagement between stakeholders and making programmes more contextually informed and relevant (Sherry & Schulenkorf, 2016). The importance of relationships is reinforced by Levermore (2011) who states that when undertaken correctly PAR engages with a variety of stakeholders and builds trust, reciprocity and collaboration between research participants and communities, ensuring authentic local voices are not missed or dismissed in the evaluation process.

Whilst I support the previous points the reality of applying PAR is not without complications. This is particularly relevant to the realisation of participant outcomes. Ultimately, the application of PAR within IRSS (2019) did not realise the intended transformative outcomes for the participants. I will discuss these complexities, and possible solutions, in the following section.

3.1.2 Participant Outcomes

Reflecting and engaging with participants to explore, equally and collaboratively, programme outcomes can increase the likelihood of participant concerns being acted upon and in turn, positive outcomes being realised. One of the barriers to developing appropriate educational outcomes in SfD is discussed by Schweisfurth (2015) who states that when monitoring outcomes success is directly influenced by what is measurable. The reason for this is that international organisations require to know whether focused investment has led to improvements in terms of outcome. This leads to policy being informed numerically and leaves little room for approaches that are not easily measurable. Outcomes in SfD projects are further influenced by several factors including curriculum design, professional development, learning materials, location, amenities, and the local community (Riddell & Nino-Zarazua, 2015).

My experiences of advocating for, and employing, PAR has shown that engaging participants within the research process increases opportunities to experience local contexts, take local knowledge and perspectives seriously, and understand the impact of projects on the community (Mwaanga & Adeosun, 2017). There are, however, significant concerns with how research has been traditionally undertaken within SfD and the impact of this on realising positive social change outcomes for participants. Adams and Harris (2014) state that traditional approaches to evidence building within SfD have been narrow, constraining and have sat within a positivist paradigm. Too often agency has been skewed towards those in a position of power, marginalising local voices and reinforcing unequal relationships (Levermore & Beacom, 2012). This process devalues local knowledge through unexamined hegemonic perspectives (Nicholls, Giles & Seta, 2010), making it difficult for actors to extricate themselves and to assert local perspectives.

Development interventions are subsequently framed as helping the global South move into the future – not necessarily a future of their own imagining, however, but a future as exemplified by the West (Kothari, 2010). When agency for local stakeholders is reduced and local voices are restricted, relationships within SfD are more likely to be skewed towards the international than they are to decentred local contexts (Levermore & Beacom, 2012). The universalisation of the issues faced by people and communities in the global South has created a tendency to universalise development objectives across diverse and unique contexts resulting in an oversimplification of the inequalities that exist within individuals and communities (Mwaanga & Prince, 2016). Through an oversimplified perspective of the global South, as highlighted in JSFD (2017), a well-intentioned and ambitious project failed to fully understand the complex realities of development in diverse and challenging communities (Hayhurst, 2009).

This in turn, led to a prescriptive action on the part of participants within the SfD project in Cape Town rather than a critical approach that understood wider social, political, cultural, and economic inequalities that exist within their everyday, lived reality (Mwaanga & Prince, 2016). Opportunities were limited for participants to engage with their own knowledge and experience to make sense of their worlds and themselves and thereby to influence how they act (Hayhurst, Giles & Wright, 2016). The project was not designed for local needs, and it was local stakeholders and participants who were expected to adapt to and integrate the proposals of a global North based organisation. This has clear implications for the realisation of appropriate and valid programme outcomes.

SfD outcomes are highly dependent on the specifics of any country context and that provision is unevenly distributed and subject to varied contextual influences across different localities (Lindsey, 2017). In support of this perspective JSFD (2017) highlighted a lack of engagement with understanding these varied contextual factors in relation to participant outcomes. This oversight ensured that local practices and knowledge, socio-cultural, political, and economic

contexts and the needs and desires of participants were missed (Hartman & Kwauk, 2011). A lack of engagement with participants reduced the project's capacity to interrogate the relations of power that underlie the project. This limited the development of authentic dialogue, genuine democratic action, and critical consciousness (Giulianotti, Hognestad & Spaaij, 2016).

There are, however, a multitude of different approaches which can increase the likelihood of realising positive social change outcomes for participants. In IRSS (2019) the inclusion in the research process of practitioners and participants through PAR gave opportunities to those who struggled to be heard, legitimising their voice, and putting it on an equal footing (Adams & Harris, 2014). Changes to the distribution of power and control in IRSS (2019) increased the opportunity for people to engage collectively and collaboratively (Hartmann and Kwauk, 2011). Appropriate levels of collaboration positioned local actors at the centre of the process, and contributed to a *'shift in power where local participants can come to own the research'* (Spaaij et al, 2017, p.7). This is the understanding that people's local knowledge is both valuable and critical for informing practitioners and scholars about the value of projects within a real-world context.

Whilst I concur with the points raised above in relation to collaboration and distribution of power, conducting participatory research and ensuring positive outcomes for participants remains a highly challenging process. In IRSS (2019) I reflected on the challenges associated with co-producing a participatory community sport initiative and the intention of realising positive outcomes for participants. The complexity of applying PAR methods to developing social cohesion through sport within the borough was underestimated. I highlighted in IRSS (2019) the potential limitations of both sport as a stand-alone entity being used to address highly complex issues such as social cohesion, as well as the application of PAR in this context.

One of the reasons for applying PAR in SfD research is to advance the possibilities for social transformation. This can be explored at an individual or community level, or in the case of IRSS (2019) both. A social transformation framework was applied in IRSS (2019) to address the complex issue of social cohesion in an ethnically divided borough. Castles (2001, p.14) defines the study of social transformation as the '*analysis of transnational connectedness and the way in which this affects national societies, local communities, and individuals*'. A social transformation framework can play an important role in determining change within society as it can be utilised to address macro level issues which impact significantly on inequity in people's lives. The rationale for applying a social transformation framework in IRSS (2019) was that social transformation in the 21st century is heavily influenced by our global and interconnected world. These connections are present in all areas of social and cultural life. As national boundaries are broken down and society becomes more diverse, local autonomy is reduced and people become '*increasingly interconnected and mutually dependent*' (Castles, 2001, p.14).

Achieving transformative outcomes requires structural barriers that reinforce inequity to be overcome. As Ball (1998) states, applying a social transformative framework to address issues of inequity, requires embracing local politics, culture, traditions and the processes of interpretation and struggle. Local politics, culture and tradition provide both distinctive opportunities and constraints in relation to thinking and practices. In turn, this extends our understanding of complex local, national, and global processes and contexts which are essential foundations for the advancement of equity (Penney, 2017). Current structural constraints that are an antithesis to addressing inequity, promoting inclusion, and implementing transformative pedagogy require challenge and reform. Challenge and reform should begin with practitioners within SfD through the process of critical reflection.

3.1.3 Reflective Practice

In order to frame this discussion on reflective practice it is important to discuss the reflective processes that I have undertaken throughout my published articles. In relation to this process I concur with Penney et al (2018) in that an ongoing process reflexivity is necessary to ensure that researchers keep asking critical questions that challenge assumptions that underpin current practices. It is important to acknowledge Paulo Freire's influence on my ongoing reflective practice, particularly reflexivity and praxis. Freire's concept of reflection is based on *'praxis as a fusion of experience, on a past-present continuum, involving reflection, dialogue and social action. In this way, theory informs practice and practice informs theory, never separating knowledge from action and action from knowledge'* (Ledwith, 2018, p.117). In building upon my understanding of reflection, dialogue, and social action throughout the completion of my published articles I have developed an understanding of three distinct but interrelated forms of reflexivity; personal, functional, and disciplinary (Finlay & Gough, 2003). Through personal reflexivity I was aware of myself as unfinished; of being incomplete as a researcher. The unfinished character of human beings necessitate that praxis is a continuous activity (Freire, 1972). Transitioning from my understanding of myself as a researcher in JSFD (2017) to the researcher that I became in IRSS (2019), RPCE (2018) and IJSPP (2020) was a personal process of 'becoming'. Personal and critical enquiry provided the opportunity to reflect on what I had learned about myself and others through shared experiences and how this may impact upon future behaviour.

The process of functional reflection enabled an exploration of my role as a researcher and how my knowledge, experiences and perceptions impacted upon specific research projects. This created the opportunity for me to explore my own reality through critical reflection. Critique of my actions in JSFD (2017) enabled me to move from a situation where I had knowledge of

my reality to a situation where I was able to perceive the causes of that reality (Freire, 1972). In transitioning from JSFD (2017) to IRSS (2019) I undertook what Nicholls (2009) identifies as the requirement to decenter myself through challenging the traditional relationship of objective control between researchers and participants. I was required to engage in a reflexive way with the collective and negotiated research design and the data collection methods in order to take into consideration the dynamics that played a part in the research process.

Through disciplinary reflexivity I explored how specific research phenomenon sat within a larger discussion of theory and method (Whitley & Johnson, 2015). Disciplinary reflexivity enabled me to explore different forms of society, question the distinction between facts and values and challenge widely held perspectives in policy, politics, and ideology (Schuurman, 2009). Through raising my consciousness around the variety of methodologies and methods that I was engaging with I was able to develop in greater depth my understanding of the complexity of research and practice (Yang, 2004). Further to this, it was important for me to reflect upon the additional political and relational layers of reflexivity required to enable a critical evaluation of empowerment and participation. This was about reflecting not just on the process of data capture at the micro level but also to reflect on the wider socio-political factors that impact upon practice at the macro level. This reflection on macro level factors was also highly relevant in the production of RPCE (2018) and IJSPP (2020).

When undertaking PAR in IRSS (2019), I sought to engage in a reflexive way with the negotiated research design and the data collection methods. The aim was to take into consideration the dynamics that play a part in the knowledge creation process. The most significant challenge in applying PAR was the requirement to incrementally relinquish control of the process to the participants. This created a highly challenging set of circumstances. Ceding control within participatory research can be a daunting and painful process as it can distort the original vision for the research. This is what Nicholls (2009) describes as a shift in

positionality that entails the researcher being receptive to new cultural understanding throughout the research process and through allowing control to be extended to participants beyond the initial stage of negotiation.

Oxford and Spaaij (2017) argue that for SfD programmes to achieve their social transformation objectives they are required to move beyond a basic engagement and participation focus for its own sake and instead seek to empower participants through providing the opportunity for decision-making and self-governance. This was the aim within IRSS (2019) with the intention to increase the level of collaboration to establish dialogue and promote critical discussion and reflection among practitioners and participants. In this context SfD organisations/practitioners are required to create spaces for critical reflection on issues of justice, equity, and power (Wright et al, 2016).

Whilst critical reflection is essential, I contend that providing opportunities for both practitioners and participants to act upon these reflections is even more important. This is described by Freire (1972) as praxis. The dialectics of reflection and action are understood as a process of critical self-reflection. This is because human nature is expressed through intentional, reflective, meaningful activity situated within dynamic historical and cultural contexts (Freire, 1972). Knowledge emerges only through invention and re-invention, through the restless, impatient, continuing, hopeful inquiry human beings pursue in the world, with the world, and with each other (Freire, 1972). The transition from advocating PAR in JSFD (2017) and applying it in IRSS (2019) was a process of praxis. Engaging with PAR through praxis involved problem identification and analysis, a plan of action to address the problem, the implementation of the plan and an analysis and evaluation of the action (Duncan-Andrade & Morrell, 2008). The process in IRSS (2019) involved dialogue among people to understand critically the social structures and ideologies that shaped and controlled their daily lives and practices (Torres & Mercado, 2004).

Svensson & Woods (2016) state that developing valid and appropriate educational outcomes requires an in-depth exploration of the realities faced by SfD organisations in evolving their education practices. Praxis, in this context, is the concrete work of understanding and changing conditions through further action, critical reflection, and a commitment to transformative action (Freire, 1976). This exploration should focus on the topics and pedagogical models that underpin programmes as the *'mere presence of educational values or educational programming does not guarantee positive outcomes'* (Svensson, Hancock & Hums, 2016, p.510).

3.1.4 Concluding Comments

In JSFD (2017) I identified the flaws in the research process and advocated for the adoption of participatory approaches to research in SfD. This critical reflection of the process was developed from my own experience and from the growing body of literature on participatory research in SfD. The paper concluded with a call for reflexive and collaborative approaches to research with PAR being advocated to realise increased participant engagement. My reflection led to the undertaking of PAR within IRSS (2019). I argue in the article that PAR can build on the lived experiences of participants and the promotion of participant agency. I contend that the realisation of these benefits through participatory approaches to research in SfD can increase participant engagement and provide the opportunity for positive social change to occur.

In terms of the realisation of participant outcomes JSFD (2017) argued that there was an over simplified perspective of the communities in which the project was delivered. This perspective failed to fully realise the complexities of development which had further implications for the intended project outcomes. There was a lack of engagement with wider contextual factors that impact upon the success of the project. Whilst I addressed these limitations in IRSS (2019)

through positioning participants at the centre of the research process, complexities were evident throughout. I underestimated both the capacity for a sport project to address a macro level issue such as social cohesion and for PAR to be embraced fully by participants who felt marginalised and powerless to instigate meaningful change. The main flaw within the project was in its attempt to address a macro level issue through a micro level project. The project, in its design and delivery, did not have the capacity to overcome the existing structural barriers that limited the capacity to address the issue of social cohesion.

In acknowledging the challenges faced in IRSS (2019) the article remains influential due to its critical and reflective analysis. It provided an open and honest account of the complexities and challenges of undertaking PAR. Reflection on, and honesty about, conducting participatory research are fundamental to our understanding of how to increase participant engagement and realise relevant and appropriate participant outcomes. In exploring and applying PAR my published work has contributed to the idea that participant voices and perspectives must be foregrounded in SfD if beneficial and equitable outcomes are to be secured and sustained.

3.2 Addressing Inequity

This section explores how inequity can be addressed through education in SfD programmes. This section is guided by findings from IJSPP (2020), SES (2022) and JSFD (2017) and is driven by the principle that those who design, deliver, and analyse education do so from the understanding that they would be prepared to live with the consequences of outcomes if it were, they who were subject to any injustice (IJSPP, 2020). The intention is to provide a clear picture of the challenges associated with the design and delivery of equitable education in SfD within the complex reality of prevailing global structures of power, wealth, and knowledge (Black, 2017). This will be undertaken through analysis of how equity is defined, its relationship to

education and social justice, and by discussing how my published articles have explored power disparities and how they can contribute to the development of equity in SfD.

IJSPP (2020) was the first article to critically analyse the UK government flagship primary schools physical education policy through a social justice lens. The engagement with Rawls Theory of Justice was significant for my own learning around the issues of equity and social justice and has subsequently influenced the approach to my most recent article (SES, 2022). It has also been important in terms of developing my knowledge and understanding of policy and its impact on practice. IJSPP (2020) highlights disparities between policy design and enactment in relation to equity, and I contend that this perspective is highly relevant to understanding the impact of policy on SfD practice.

To analyse the ways in which inequity can be addressed in SfD it is important to explore the complexity associated with defining equity. The rationale for this is that equity is often conflated with the concept of equality, yet equity must include, and at the same time transcend equality. Equity also includes the concept of social justice and therefore can remove itself from the constraints of equality. This is based upon the understanding that equality is not necessarily fair (Castelli, Ragazzi & Crescentini, 2012). Based upon this understanding, any analysis of equity in SfD should be approached from an understanding that equity, to a large extent, cannot be separated from wider socio-economic contexts. It is related to various aspects of the life of a community. Reflecting on what equity means within a community means focusing on issues such as social segregation, disability, and other forms of discrimination (Castelli, Ragazzi & Crescentini, 2012).

Whilst few people would deny the aspirational goal of equity within SfD and therefore, society, there will inevitably be disagreements regarding appropriate ways and means of advancing the principle of equity (Brookover & Lezotte, 1981). In seeking to address this concern, IJSPP

(2020) applied Rawls Theory of Justice to the analysis of physical education policy. This application is based on two principles of justice which are highly relevant for an analysis of inequity within education policy and subsequent injustices within society. The first principle is concerned with equal basic liberties for all. The second principle focuses on fair equality of opportunity to address the balance of inequity. The value in applying Rawls' conception of social justice was that it sought to remedy disadvantage through advocating for a fairer distribution of opportunities and resources. It also attempts to define what is both just and unjust. A socially just society requires every individual to have equal opportunities to transform their lives positively (Miller, 1999) and, requires addressing cultural and economic injustices (Frazer, 1998). Findings in IJSPP (2020) correlate with Gerdin et al (2019) in that the quest for social justice should focus on further problematizing affirmative and hierarchical educational practice. I argue that any attempt to structurally embed social justice practices is constrained by the contexts in which education is practised. A transition towards a more equitable model of practice is inevitably influenced by the nature of equal or unequal power relations.

Giulianotti (2011) discussed the policy domain of social justice within SfD. The domain consists of organisations that seek to challenge the dominance of top-down orientated domains (neo-liberal; interventionist and strategic). The design and delivery of education across, and within a social justice domain, is influenced by symbiotic relationships linked to issues of funding, policy goals and intended outcomes. Developing education within SfD will require organisations to traverse across and between different policy domains. Ultimately,

If inequalities are to cease to be of significance, and if promises of social justice, such as 'sport for all' are to be realised, then the analysis of policy needs to be related to broader relations of power in the culture of both sport and society (IJSPP, 2020, p.19)

Such a position requires different stakeholders within SfD to realise the impact of power disparities and the disjuncture between policy intentions and the reality of practice. In relation to connecting with national policy objectives, JSFD (2017) provides an important example. The project that was analysed within the article developed partnerships with two governmental departments. A requirement of the partnership was to incorporate the aims of the new South African Coaching Framework and the National Sport and Recreation Plan. Alongside connecting the project to national policy, the partnerships were complicated through the complex structure and requirements of the different organisations involved (JSFD, 2017). This complex structure was due to multi-level alliances that incorporated the organisation, its funder, the local governmental departments, and the participants. These conflicting dynamics were further influenced by the political landscape in Cape Town and notable tensions around legitimacy, autonomy, power imbalances and resource dependency (Collison et al, 2016). The issues that resulted from these partnerships were instrumental in some of the failings of the project identified in JSFD (2017) and impacted on the prioritisation of the participants:

For the organisation to develop in the way that it wants, the interests of the community in which it serves must come first. The partnerships with the government departments have been highly beneficial, yet it is important to be aware of how their future agenda may be in conflict with both the needs of the community and the future direction and development of LETS

(JSFD, 2017, p.24)

The danger of prioritising policy objectives and the requirements of partner organisations is that participant voice was marginalised within the project. If top-down approaches are prioritised over a social justice approach, a set of circumstances is created where SfD programmes come to be viewed by marginalised communities as complicit with dominant interests (Giulianotti, 2011). In this context, they cannot be equitable. This issue is reinforced through the difficulty in gaining an in-depth contextual understanding of the communities in

which development is taking place (Black, 2009). This can be addressed through embedding collaborative processes that promote hope, trust, humility, and respect through moving beyond the power imbalance of traditional participant-practitioner relationships and towards collective action (Oxford & Spaaij, 2017). I argue in SES (2022) that through equalising power within SfD organisations, a collaborative and dialogical approach can develop participants as active social agents in the development and realisation of social transformation. The acceptance of this position is required to resist unequal symbiosis where the interests of top-down actors predominate (Black, 2017), and ultimately, deliver equitable, inclusive, and socially just education within SfD programmes.

As realised through the research process in JSFD (2017) dominant groups strive to control and organise the system through various mechanisms and strategies. This in turn, has a significant influence on the knowledge, perceptions, and values of the various communities that constitute society (Nichol, 2011). Education discourse and the policy processes from which it derives are dominated by issues of funding and resources. These agendas squeeze out space for serious consideration of what is a meaningful, relevant, equitable, and valued education (Aikman, 2011). I addressed these agendas in SES (2022) through an analysis of critical and dialogical pedagogy in SfD. The qualitative systematic review identified that traditional education approaches within SfD were focused on a Western perception of education. This focus is a significant factor in undermining autonomy, reducing opportunity for meaningful dialogue, and repressing the ability for individuals/communities to exercise agency and/or engage in independent action (Nichol, 2011).

When disparities in SfD practice exist, they do so because of the (un)intended domination of Northern knowledge, world views and expertise. Addressing power disparities and the disconnections that they reinforce remains a significant challenge for SfD policy, programmes, and participants. I argued in JSFD (2017) that disparity between Northern knowledge and the

reality of application creates complex interactions that limit the capacity for equitable programme objectives to be fully realised. These complexities were reinforced through programme design which was a top-down form of intervention that lacked cultural understanding, imposed Northern values, failed to address the complexity of implementation, and lacked a specific focus on the needs and wants of communities (Black, 2009). The main concern to emerge from JSFD (2017) is whether SfD has the capacity to address wider social and political issues across diverse and unique contexts (Jarvie, 2011; Coakley, 2015; Mwaanga & Prince, 2016). I maintain that sport has the capacity to address these issues but only if developed in a collaborative and equitable way.

The development of collaborative and equitable SfD projects requires organisations, scholars, and practitioners to consider wider macro level factors that impact upon programme design and delivery. Whilst there are inherent power disparities within SfD, the situation can be more nuanced than a binary position between North and South or top-down and bottom-up. The notion that SfD is built and sustained on global North policies and norms about what needs to be developed through sport, who should be involved, where and when it should take place and how impact is assessed has been called into question (McSweeney et al, 2019). SfD organisations and local actors are connected to differing aspects of local cultural contexts yet are also affected both directly and indirectly by wider forces (Lindsey & Grattan, 2012). Within SfD top-down, global North approaches and bottom-up development organisation are characterized by relatively close relationships and in many instances, these have been highly dependent. Black (2017, p.14) describes this as '*inequitable symbiosis*' where actors from both sides have a *compelling interest in sustaining their complementarities and obfuscating their differences*.

I know from the experiences of developing, delivering, and analysing my own SfD project in Cape Town that there are benefits for participants and stakeholders in such a circumstance.

This being said, and as highlighted in JSFD (2017), the nature of the relationship generally remains inequitable with top-down actors and interests remaining dominant. Black (2017) describes different actors working across different orientations of SfD as fluid and permeable with organisations straddling the boundaries of top-down and bottom-up development with varying degrees of regularity and strategic acumen. This is identified by Black (2017, p.10) as a '*grand pragmatic synthesis*'. This requires organisations to move beyond simplistic definitions of relationships between North and South and to explore the potential within more symbiotic relationships. An acceptance of symbiosis does not mean an acceptance of unequal symbiosis. When opportunities present themselves, local capabilities and interests can be achieved through informal operations of local SfD organisations. These informal operations enable the disruption of taken for granted norms of global North hegemony/global South dependency (McSweeney et al, 2019).

Such disruption can increase the likelihood of equitable outcomes being realised within SfD programmes. This requires a move towards a collective position between programmes and their participants with an emphasis on dialogue, negotiation, and collaboration. As I argued in SES (2022) there is a requirement for SfD organisations to take greater consideration of local and national perspectives rather than imposing predetermined pedagogical criteria. Incorporating pedagogy that is culturally empathetic and socially empowering will have a greater impact on the lives and futures of programme participants (Giulianotti, Hognestad & Spaaij, 2016).

3.2.1 Concluding comments

My analysis of a specific macro level physical education policy through a social justice lens, exposed disparities between policy design at the macro level and policy enactment at the micro level. I argued that the attempt to address inequity through policy were constrained by the structures of, and disparities within, education itself. Through further analysis of critical

pedagogy and social justice I have described inequitable processes in the design and delivery of SfD. Through the analysis of these issues my published work has shown that for equity to be realised SfD policy and practice is required to directly address existent power disparities. I argue that disparity between Northern knowledge and the reality of application creates complex interactions that limit the capacity for equitable programme objectives to be fully realised. Addressing inequity requires an exploration of the disconnect between macro level policy and micro level practice through the promotion and enactment of dialogue, negotiation, and collaboration.

3.3 Inclusive practice for social justice

As discussed in the previous section the concept of social justice is fundamental in addressing inequity and power disparities within SfD. I also content that embedding the principle of social justice in SfD is fundamental the development of inclusive practice. Inclusion is generally understood around the world as part of a human rights agenda that demands access to, and equity in, education (Florian, 2008). It is about bringing people together, rather than a process in which policy makers, organisations and practitioners can pick and choose those they see as of value and excluding those who are deemed too difficult or complex to make a valued contribution. Inclusion is seeing the value in including all people and the learning, understanding and awareness that this can bring. In my published work I have argued that successful implementation of inclusion for social justice requires *'treating all students as individuals and working without prejudice'* (RPCE, 2019, p.336). The concepts of inclusion and social justice are interconnected. There cannot be one without the other.

3.3.1 Inclusive Practice

In RPCE (2018) I reflected on my experiences as an inclusive educator over a ten-year period. The article focused on the historical development of inclusive practice, current issues, and

future concerns of a further education college as it sought to navigate a complex social, economic, and political landscape. The employment of an auto-ethnographic methodology alongside interviews with key actors enabled an inclusive approach to the research process. This ensured that my own and other voices were given a platform to address the marginalisation of inclusive practice within the college.

Auto-ethnography and the supporting interviews within RPCE (2018) connected personal stories to social phenomenon. The key benefit of this was in understanding the broader experiences of inclusive practice through dialogue, both including and beyond, the self. This was an approach that valued the voices of others through exploring layered accounts and providing the opportunity for perceptions from more than one point of view (Spry, 2001). If the research process in RPCE (2018) had relied purely on my own voice and my own reflections I would have been unable to tell the full story. Many people that I worked with including learning support assistants, teaching colleagues and college managers all had their own story to tell. They had all played a key role in forming, developing, and delivering the inclusive ethos within the college through being part of a specific culture and embracing a particular cultural identity (Ellis, Adams & Bochner, 2011).

The article was important for me on both a personal and professional level as it re-confirmed my passion for, and belief in, inclusive education. I am proud of the article as it is a very personal piece of work. I lived the experience presented within the article for ten years and was passionate about the college, the students and the people who worked hard to support them. In RPCE (2018) I made the case for inclusive education and identified the opportunities that inclusion can bring for staff, students, and organisations:

It brought students and staff together that would otherwise not have interacted and, in the process, prompted conversations, reflections and learning that would otherwise not have happened for all concerned (RPCE, 2018 p.337).

Whilst my position on the value of inclusive education is clear, there remain issues with how inclusion is approached in education currently. The terms inclusion and inclusive practice have become ubiquitous across education. Whilst the concept of inclusion has, in many ways, become common within political and educational discourse there remains disagreement and discussions amongst academic and professionals about what constitutes effective inclusive practice (Fitzgerald & Stride, 2012; Vickerman, 2007a). I concur with Atkins (2016) that inclusion is a misunderstood and misused concept that has, to some degree, become a taken for granted assumption. I reflected on this perspective in RPCE (2018) regarding the challenges of implementing an inclusive approach:

The path chosen was a difficult one, developing an understanding amongst staff of the value of inclusion within a sports department, and promoting the view that all students have a right to the same education as their peers (RPCE, 2018 p.337).

This challenge reflects the position outlined by Dyson (2005) in that inclusion is a fundamental principle for some, but no more than convenient language for others. There is a significant challenge in realising the benefits of inclusive practice through a deficit discourse that limits the possibility of working towards inclusion (Petrie, Devcich & Fitzgerald, 2018). This highlights the challenge in moving towards a more inclusive model and whether practitioners can move beyond superficial modifications and question what it means to be inclusive (Petrie, Devcich & Fitzgerald, 2018). The conflict that is created from differing perspective of inclusive practice was evident in RPCE (2018, p,342) in that:

conflict derives from the belief that one approach, one solution (inclusion) does not fit all. Those who believe fully in the value of inclusion refuse to make the paradigm shift away from this belief, whereas others no longer believe that the old paradigm satisfactorily solves the problem or explains the current reality.

Conceptual clarity regarding inclusion has been reduced through related concepts such as ‘mainstreaming’ and ‘integration’ (Fitzgerald & Stride, 2012). Between the enactment of inclusion within policy, and its possible enactment as practice rest a host of complicated and compounding factors. As I argued in RPCE (2018) there is a disconnection between macro level policy and funding and micro level practices. The outcomes of practice are inevitably affected by national, regional, and institutional factors that reflect their history, politics, and ideologies. These factors are always conditioned by distributions of authority and economic resources (Evans, 2014b). The desire to explore these factors further encouraged me to develop research projects that explored the issues of equity, inclusion and social justice within and across SfD and education.

3.3.2 Social Justice

Social justice can be realised in SfD when free and equal persons who are not dominated or manipulated from a position of political or social inferiority can create, through cooperation, a project that benefits the more and the less advantaged members (Rawls, 1971). Whilst I acknowledge that Rawls’s Theory of Justice is a complex theoretical construct, it provides an relevant framework for theorising inequity and social justice in SfD. RPCE (2018) and IJSP (2020) sought to address this disparity through analysing how macro level factors have impacted upon micro level practices. In relation to micro/macro disparities I agree with Penney et al (2018) who state that inclusion is a critical political agenda. This is because inclusion for social justice must not be solely a matter of access or as an act of accomplishment but rather

as an on-going political process that must be continuously and routinely achieved (Evans, 2014a).

To explore concerns around social justice in the Physical Education and School Sport Premium (PESSP) policy in England, IJSP (2020) employed a mixed method case study methodology. A mixed method case study was a valid form of enquiry for the exploration of a broad scope of complex issues (Harrison et al, 2017). In depth consideration was required for the nature of the case within this bounded context, including historical, physical, institutional, and political factors (Stake, 2008). Whilst equitable in approach, I acknowledge that in the mixed method case study undertaken in IJSP (2020) knowledge was subjective with multiple realities being experienced by different people, including myself, in several different ways (Dasgupta, 2015). Reflecting on equity and social justice, in IJSP (2020) I argued that the PESSP policy, in part due to the autonomy of implementation, failed to realise its inherent social justice agenda. Equity will remain unobtainable when the central tenets of the reproduction of privilege remain uncontested (IJSP, 2020). Social justice requires recognition of different education systems, different bodies of knowledge and different worldviews so that they can become resources to support young people in their fast changing and interconnected worlds (Aikman, 2010, p.21). Social justice can provide a rationale for a policy focus on education quality as *'education quality is a political issue and as such participation in deciding about what are the valued outcomes of education and valued processes to support these should be a matter of debate'* (Tikly & Barrett, 2011, p.6). My published articles argue that to realise social justice principles requires circumnavigating the complex processes of education in an unequal society. Addressing these complexities requires a desire to understand the complex social dynamics of the communities within which education takes place (Wilson-Strydom & Okkolin, 2015).

Developing inclusive and equitable education programmes requires a shift from providing access to education to providing quality of education (Heyneman & Bommi, 2016). As I concluded in IJSPP (2020) the quest for social justice in education requires a focus on further problematizing affirmative and hierarchical educational practice. The rationale for this is that social justice teaching strategies are enabled and constrained by the contexts in which they are practised (Gerdin et al, 2019). Findings in IJSPP (2020) concur with Riddell & Nino-Zarazua (2015) in that developing education policy and intended outcomes through the principle of social justice and inclusive practice can never be an exact science as there cannot be one established blueprint of what to do that can be applied generally to all. To address such concerns policy makers and practitioners are required to pay sufficient attention to quality improvement so as not to create a second-class system for those without alternative choices (Riddell & Nino-Zarazua, 2015).

3.3.3 Inclusion for social justice in sport for development

In RPCE (2018) and IJSPP (2020), I argued that to embrace inclusion for social justice requires the development of practice as a shared endeavour. In this context, deficit discourses and narrow conceptualisations of inclusion must be challenged if policy makers and practitioners are to embrace genuinely inclusive ideals (Vickerman, 2007a). Within RPCE (2018) I concluded that an inclusive approach should be driven through an exploration of the opportunities and constraints associated with historical, economic, social, political, and cultural factors that influence the development of genuine inclusive practice. This requires challenging traditional norms and accepted practices that are embedded in dominant pedagogy and policy discourses (Penney et al, 2018).

To embrace equity in SfD programmes requires social justice to be a key driver regarding the development of educational outcomes. In IJSPP (2020) I stated that the main barrier to

achieving social justice in education, is when there is inequity through power imbalances between policy, organisations, and participants. Power imbalances can be addressed through programmes being designed through the principle of inclusive practice. Seeking social justice in education through developing an in depth understanding of communities and their needs can be achieved through the development and application of transformational pedagogy. In SES (2022) I analysed critical pedagogy, social justice, and social transformation through Freire's (1972) concept of dialogical and anti-dialogical action. The internationally relevant results, in part, explored the role of social justice in the development of transformational pedagogy.

In SES (2022) my findings demonstrated that developing a social justice-informed pedagogical approach would enable SfD organisations to further challenge their own values, attitudes and beliefs whilst critically exploring the wider social implications of their practice. My findings concur with Penney et al (2018) who state that to move beyond narrow, and potentially exclusive, conceptions of inclusion and social justice requires a willingness to question assumptions that underpin established norms of practice that reinforce inequities. Through the recommendations stated in SES (2022) I argue that addressing inequities can be achieved through embracing dialogical and transgressive conceptualisations of social justice.

To realise this objective, I have shown in my published work that time should be spent examining the philosophical context for inclusion and articulating a clear recognition for the rationale and arguments behind inclusive education. This requires inclusion in SfD to be understood as a process that evolves and changes over time and therefore requires regular review and adaption (Vickerman, 2007a). To implement this process there is a need to move beyond adapting activities to look at how curriculum, pedagogy and practice can become a shared endeavour in which the voices of all participants are heard (Petrie, Devcich & Fitzgerald, 2018). Therefore, and in concurrence with Ainscow (1999) I believe that successful

inclusion rests upon demonstrating positive attitudes and a commitment to inclusion whilst embedding inclusive values as an integral aspect of pedagogical practice.

3.3.4 Concluding comments

I have argued that the term inclusion remains contested and in certain instances, ubiquitous. It can be misunderstood and misused, and I contend that it has in many instances, become a taken for granted assumption. This marginalises genuinely inclusive ideals and limits dialogue as to how a fully inclusive model of practice can be realised. I have argued that there remains a disconnect between macro level policy and funding, and micro level practice in SfD and education. This disconnect is entrenched through policy and funding that limits the capacity for organisations and practitioners to embed inclusive ideals. The fundamental principles of inclusion are consistently under threat (Evans, 2014a). This requires resistance not compliance to realise genuinely inclusive and socially just policy and practice.

I contend that the desire to address complex social dynamics and the development of education policy and practice within an unequal society are fundamental to the development of inclusive and socially just practices. In SfD an inclusive approach requires an analysis of the opportunities and constraints that are associated with history, economics, society, politics, and culture. Traditional norms of practice require challenge through a social justice lens. This is about connecting the principles of inclusion and social justice to develop education practices that can contribute to the realisation of positive social change.

3.4 Transformational Pedagogy

My interest in SfD derives from the understanding that it utilises sport to address wider social issues and contribute to different development circumstances and contexts (Levermore, 2008). It is this understanding of the value of SfD, particularly its capacity to contribute to educational objectives, that influenced my decision to develop my own SfD organisation in Cape Town.

The project delivered two specific programmes. The first was for school physical education curriculum co-ordinators and the second was delivered to future sports leaders in a community context. To understand the impact of these programmes, JSFD (2017) focused on the pedagogical approach employed. This reflective process developed from my desire to develop my knowledge and understanding of pedagogy in SfD, their impact on participants and their capacity to deliver intended social change outcomes. The approach to pedagogy within the programmes was didactic. Education was done to participants rather than with. Didactic approaches subjugated knowledge about broader and fundamental social and environmental conditions. There was a lack of opportunity for dialogue and collaboration for participants in terms of their opportunity to shape pedagogy within the project (Mwaanga & Prince, 2016).

It is for these reasons that within JSFD (2017) and SES (2022) I advocated for the future application of critical pedagogy within SfD as it has the potential to develop a more holistic model of practice. This can be achieved through embedding critical reflection, empowerment and challenging competing and conflicting discourses that seek to address the iniquities in access, participation, and outcomes (Kirk, 2006). In this context, curricula would focus on critical sociocultural perspectives, alongside negotiated and student-centred pedagogies to allow for students to take ownership and responsibility for their own learning (Penney et al, 2018). The practical application of critical pedagogy can fundamentally change the way in which education is conceived and organised, increasing the validity of, and meaning for, young people as:

the imposition of a curriculum for the perceived benefit of a specific community with only a limited understanding of its validity and worth within a specific context ensures that the process is inevitably flawed (JSFD, 2017, p.26).

Critical pedagogy has the capacity to support this change through the '*dual aim of educating about social inequity, identifying and highlighting oppressive structures, and educating for emancipation, actively dismantling oppressive structures and engaging in change*' (Tinning, 2017, p.288). To be transformative within their practice, practitioners are required to embrace sociocultural perspectives through reflecting on their pedagogical approaches and how they interact with young people (Lynch and Curtner-Smith, 2019). This increases the opportunity to promote social justice, address cultural inequities and develop a pedagogical approach that is not imposed but *created collaboratively to ensure a higher level of relevance for those for whom it is intended* (JSFD, 2017, p.26).

I accept the flaws in the approach that was undertaken in the design and delivery of my SfD project in Cape Town but contend that critically reflecting upon those flaws has helped to develop my understanding of how dialogical and critical approaches to education programmes within SfD could be applied. Based upon both my teaching practice and subsequent research on critical pedagogy (JSFD, 2017; SES, 2022), I concur with Penney et al (2018); Tinning (2017) and Lynch & Curtner-Smith (2019) that the application of critical pedagogy can fundamentally change the way education is conceived and organised.

The challenge of applying critical pedagogy is complicated by the requirements for projects to fit into a standardised and quantifiable framework for the benefit of donors and other stakeholders. This requirement was reflected in JSFD (2017) through the complexities of working in partnership between different organisations and stakeholders based in both the global North and the global South. These complexities relate to the capacity to empower and demarginalise people within the structural constraints in which programmes are expected to operate (Oxford and Spaaij, 2017). In this context, I concur with Wright et al (2016) in that, to be consistent with Freire's concept of critical pedagogy, SfD organisations and practitioners should create spaces for praxis on issues of justice, equity, and power. This requires an in depth

understanding of the type of programme outcomes that are envisaged, how these outcomes can be implemented through pedagogical practice and how pedagogy is connected to those envisaged outcomes clearly, and rationally.

Due to these experiences, and to explore critical pedagogy with SfD further, in SES (2022) I examined the existing body of research that addresses the practical application of critical pedagogy within physical education and SfD. Building upon the ideas developed in JSFD (2017) and IJSPP (2020), SES (2022) was the first systematic qualitative review to examine and organise the current body of research that addressed the practical application of critical pedagogy within physical education and SfD. A qualitative systematic review is a method for comparing the findings from qualitative studies, with the intention of accumulating knowledge through developing an overarching narrative, a wider generalisation, or an interpretative translation (Grant & Booth, 2009). Utilising a qualitative systematic review, I established the extent to which existing research on critical pedagogy has progressed towards addressing inequity and the implications of this progression for policy and practice (Siddaway et al, 2019). The process involved a synthesis of existing studies through the development of an overarching narrative and interpretative translation of qualitative findings (Grant & Booth, 2009). Through synthesising work from across physical education and SfD I argued that there is significant scope for exploring the ways in which each can learn from the other and to identify the possibilities for this within a development context.

SES (2022) analysed critical pedagogy through Freire's (1972) concept of dialogical and anti-dialogical action. Freire (1972) argues that effective dialogical action supports the liberation of people through their own reflection and actions upon their world to change it rather than as an act of dominance or oppression. In SES (2022) I utilised Freire's writings to argue that a dialogical and critical approach to pedagogy in SfD can go some way towards addressing these structural constraints. The rationale for this is that SfD programmes conceived in a dialogical

and critical form are more likely to exhibit some of Freire's core considerations regarding the need for interaction and raising conscientization (Knijnik et al, 2019). This requires an incremental approach that focuses on dialogical action through the creation of space for critical reflection and participant voice. This space requires to be rooted in, and informed by, local contexts and is one way addressing concerns with the application of critical pedagogy within SfD (SES, 2022). Promoting and facilitating a reflective and open culture can create historically, politically, and socially aware citizens through stimulating socio-critical reflections and exposing injustices and oppressive conditions (Wright et al, 2016).

In concurrence with Mwaanga & Adeosun (2019) I also argued in SES (2022) that embracing a dialogical approach increases opportunities for education in SfD to be democratised, allowing for more people to be heard, seen, and talked about. I explored the potential for transformation, building on the understanding that dialogue is required to be in accordance with the experiences of people rather than in direct contrast to it. Dialogue is an '*existential necessity*' (Freire, 1972, p.88), developing people's self-determination and civic engagement rather than simply reproducing the past and understanding the present. In SES (2022) I stated that dialogue promotes a deep learning experience where people can share their experiences and to use the experiences of others to develop an understanding of their own views, opinions, and assumptions.

Wright et al (2016) identify that transformational learning can be fostered through the creation of space for participant voice(s), facilitating reflective learning that is rooted in, and informed by, local contexts. It involves participants in decision making, partnering them as co-facilitators, enhancing participants' personal and collective agency and developing an inclusive approach. Embracing a dialogical approach enables the process to be democratised, allowing for more people to be heard, seen, and talked about (Mwaanga & Adeosun, 2019). This requires a complex yet flexible approach that reflects the positive and negative experiences that young

people have in their interaction with programme content (Glasby & Macdonald, 2004). Meaning is constructed through teaching and learning activities that enable young people to engage with their environment (Wright, 2004). In JSFD (2017), I criticised the pedagogical processes undertaken and the subsequent call for a dialogical and critical future for SfD pedagogy in SES (2022) reflects the requirement for increased participant involvement. The rationale for this approach is that by critically and dialogically engaging with social and cultural meanings embodied in people's experiences, learning opportunities can be created that challenge accepted assumptions and disrupt universal untruths (Burrows, 2004). In this context I agree with Tinning (2020) who states that practitioners should have criticality as the forever present lens through which they reflect on their practice and observe the educational context more generally.

In SES (2022) I identified challenges in applying critical pedagogy beyond theoretical understanding and into practical reality. Whilst critical pedagogy can facilitate small changes across several different areas, current literature does not provide evidence as to how collective or systematic change can be facilitated (Nols et al, 2018; Oxford & Spaaij, 2016). Individuals can experience a form of transformation, but the real challenge is to understand how critical pedagogy can transform communities and the provision of empirical evidence on how this can realistically be achieved (Spaij et al, 2016).

Such critiques question the suitability of critical pedagogy to be applied in SfD education programmes. Tinning (2002), in his reflections on critical pedagogy in physical education, explored an alternative pedagogical approach for addressing the concerns associated with applying critical pedagogy. He advocated for an incremental and modest critical pedagogy as an orientated way of thinking about what claims can be made in the name of pedagogy, and its claims of realising social change. This is about being circumspect in what we can claim to know and acting without certainty regarding pedagogical claims about the delivery of

emancipatory outcomes. Such a position aligns to my own political views and my own understanding of how best to incrementally realise positive social change. This position does not move us away from the critical project but enables an approach that is more likely to engage those who find the concept of critical pedagogy a challenge, both personally and professionally. Whilst Tinning (2020) recognises the downside of incrementalism to the critical project, he suggests that social reform is best achieved through incremental change stimulated by conflict and contestation over time. Essential to that conflict and contestation is rationality and reason. Intuition, emotion, and gut feeling are not a strategy for changing society. Getting this balance right is a significant challenge for organisations, practitioners and scholars who seek to maintain the critical project through the development and application of transformational pedagogy in SfD.

The social and political are present in all pedagogies, since it is the discursive nature of any practice that makes it seem natural, apolitical and asocial; the *'very idea of transformative pedagogy is to expose and problematize the already social and political in those practices'* (Ovens, 2017, p.303). These problematic perspectives of social awareness, empathy and understanding amongst future practitioners reinforces the concept that the values that a practitioner holds can be firmly entrenched and inevitably impact on practice (Shelly & McCuaig, 2019). Critical pedagogy provides the possibility for disruption, productivity, and hope (Luguetti & Oliver, 2020). It exists to disrupt the status quo and to challenge and expose the workings of power rather than to facilitate its reproduction. This ensures that critical pedagogy remains uncomfortable and unpopular at a structural level (Fitzpatrick, 2019). Further to this, a lack of critical engagement with pedagogy at an international level has resulted in unintended consequences and selective hybridisation, limiting the potential for pedagogy to impact positively on practice (Schweisfurth, 2015). In SES (2022) I state that for these concerns

to be addressed a critique of the existing social order and its attendant power relations and influence on social inequalities is required:

Exploring a critical future for SfD requires understanding the complex reality for SfD programmes and how organisations are evolving in relation to educational aims and practices (SES, 2022, p.25).

The realisation of a critical future for SfD requires actors to participate critically in the transformation of both their own experiences and of the world itself through collective resistance against hegemonic structures and inequality (Hartmann & Kwauk, 2011). Social transformation in SfD is more likely to be realised through a critical shift in curriculum and professional development that embraces dialogue, reflection, negotiation, and collaboration:

The challenge of a critical and dialogical approach to curriculum design in SfD is whether practitioners believe they can apply it and utilise it to address social justice, power, and equity (SES, 2022, p.24).

Further to this, developing pedagogy within a culture of social justice would enable SfD organisations to challenge their own values, attitudes and beliefs whilst critically exploring the wider social implications of their practice. In addressing this perspective, SES (2022) provided a series of recommendations that could be adopted internationally to create a space for critical reflection and participant voice in the development of SfD programmes. Adopting these recommendations requires dialogical action through an organisational culture that is committed to equalising power:

This space can be created in SfD curricula and professional development through a specific focus on social justice, cultural adaptation, and values through dialogue. This shift would increase the likelihood of SfD organisations being able to connect pedagogy to the type of social transformation that is both envisaged and desired (SES, 2022 p.28).

I believe that connecting pedagogy to intended project outcomes is fundamental to ensuring a critical and dialogical future for SfD. This requires utilising local knowledge and approaches that underpin educational content and suit local realities and needs (Spaaij, Oxford & Jeanes, 2016). This is based upon the understanding that successful and incremental implementation of critical pedagogy in SfD can only happen through the outcome of specific struggles that are related to specific contexts, communities, or resources (Knijnik & Luguetti, 2020).

3.4.1 Concluding comments

I concur with Kirk (2006) who argues that pedagogy should be regarded as a multidimensional concept concerned with the interactions of learning, teaching and curriculum and how they are situated within the social and physical environment. I believe that developing a dialogical approach to pedagogy would enable SfD organisations to further challenge their own values, attitudes and beliefs whilst critically exploring the wider social implications of their practice. Without dialogical action that engages with participants to ascertain their needs and wants, the likelihood of delivering transformative objectives in SfD is reduced (Spaaij et al, 2016; Mwaanga & Prince, 2016). I argue that developing a dialogical and transformative approach to pedagogical design within SfD requires an interrogation of the relations of power that underlie sport-based interventions. SfD organisations should engage participants dialogically in a mutual process of grappling with power, inequality, and identity (Hartmann & Kwauk, 2011). Embracing dialogue, negotiation and collaboration between organisations, participants and the wider community is a starting point for the incremental development of a more transformative approach (Fitzpatrick, 2019).

Having undertaken a critical and reflective synthesis of the published articles I will now reflect upon this process and present a future research agenda for addressing the four thematic areas at the intersection of sport, development and education.

Chapter 4 – Reflections and Future Directions

In reflecting upon my research and published articles this chapter will (1) explore what have I learned from my published work and the existing literature (2) present my key arguments and outline a future research agenda in relation to the four thematic areas (3) address how my research will contribute to this agenda, and (4) summarise the critical appraisal in relation to the achievement of its intended aim and objectives.

4.1 What have I learned from reflecting on my published work and the existing literature?

As I stated in my initial political reflection in section 2.1.3, I believe that adopting a rigid ideological position limits the exploration of the variety of perspectives that are available to realise positive social change through education in SfD. Being flexible opens up the opportunity to apply different theoretical frameworks and methodological approaches. Positive social change is, however, a highly complex process whether that is addressing a specific social issue within a community, educating practitioners, or seeking to develop or modify policy. Change is not a given, and requires a significant amount of hard work, engagement, cultural understanding, and relationship building. To work towards the realisation of positive social change requires scholars and practitioners to *‘effectively examine and reflect on sport and social change both as practices and sociocultural phenomena’* (Misener, Rich & Pearson, 2021, p. 3)

In working towards this aim I will maintain my current ontological, epistemological, and methodological positions. My epistemological, ontological, and methodological assumptions have formed my thinking and understanding of the world, and these have not changed throughout the process of completing this appraisal. The rationale for this is that, ontologically, I remain an idealist and epistemologically a constructivist. I believe that reality derives from people’s beliefs and perceptions of the world, their knowledge is personal subjective and unique. Their interpretations of social phenomena create new knowledge. This knowledge is

to be valued and respected in my explorations of how inequity can be addressed in SfD and education. Methodologically, I remain committed to undertaking critical qualitative research. This approach enables a broad array of methods to be employed to understand social phenomenon and people's reality within it. I have within the published articles used a variety of methods, including mixed method (quantitative and qualitative) and I intend to continue to do so.

The reflective and critical appraisal of my published work has explored ways in which participant engagement could be increased and inequity addressed. PAR improves participation through increased dialogue, collaboration, and negotiation. An equitable approach in SfD would embrace the concepts of inclusion and social justice and connect the design of pedagogy to intended programme outcomes. Through analysing the relationship between the macro and the micro in terms of policy, funding, and practice I contend that the complexities and inequities created through this relationship mitigate against equitable approaches within SfD. Resistance is required to challenge power disparities that work against the ideals of equity, inclusion, and social justice and the capacity to embed these concepts in pedagogy. Based upon the analysis presented through the four thematic areas it is my argument that when participant engagement, inequity, inclusion for social justice and transformational pedagogy are addressed and/or implemented positive social change in SfD is more likely to be realised.

Building from this position I contend that the future research agenda at the intersection of sport, education and development should focus on: (1) increasing the opportunity for participants to engage within the design and analysis of programmes and/or curriculum (2) reducing inequity through addressing power imbalances in relation to policy and practice (3) ensuring inclusion and social justice principles are enacted within practice and, (4) realising a dialogical and critical future through transformational pedagogy. The following sections will lay out how my future research will contribute to this research agenda.

4.2 What will be my contribution to the research agenda?

In the past, my work has been positioned within the community in which I previously worked (Blackburn, England) and internationally. I maintain a significant interest in the global aspects of education and SfD and intend to engage collaboratively with qualitative and participant centred international research on SfD in the future. This will require building connections with other scholars both nationally and internationally. However, following the completion of this PhD and the article that I intend to develop from it, I will initially focus on undertaking research in Scotland. I moved to Scotland four years ago and due to the pressures of full-time work and a part time PhD I have been unable to develop Scotland specific research. From my own perspective, it is important that my research contributes to the community in which I live and work. My future research in Scotland will explore, but not be limited to, participant engagement in SfD; sport politics and policy; transformative pedagogy and inclusion in physical education and SfD. It is my intention to develop research within both physical education and SfD in Scotland. The specifics of, and rationale for, the research that I intend to undertake will be discussed in the following sections.

4.2.1 Participant engagement, outcomes & reflection

Based upon my published work, specifically IRSS (2019), I have discussed how participatory approaches to research can make a significant contribution to increasing equity through increased participant engagement and improved programme outcomes. For me, participant engagement is a fundamental principle in the design, delivery, and analysis of SfD projects. This is particularly the case when seeking socially orientated programme outcomes. Ultimately, future developments should be undertaken in *‘collaboration with individuals and communities in which the programmes will be delivered, ensuring both a level of ownership for the participants and a level of cultural understanding for the organisation’* (JSFD, 2017, p.27).

This in turn should ensure that programmes are designed, delivered, and analysed in an equitable way. I have also discussed in detail how equitable principles increase the likelihood of addressing existent power disparities within SfD. To redress the balance of power within SfD and to ensure outcomes are designed and delivered equitably requires participant engagement to be central within projects.

It is important that I seek to put these views and ideas into practice through my own research and community engagement. This is the process of praxis through a response to a real situation in which I utilise my understanding and commitment to transform my own work and society (Carr and Kemmis, 1986). A continuous process of reflection, dialogue and engagement is required throughout the lifecycle of a project. Through praxis, I intend to insert myself into the local community not as a viewer but as an actor (Freire, 1976). Specifically, I will develop a community sport project in Ayr North (a borough of Ayr) which is the 20th most deprived borough in Scotland (SIMD, 2020).

Developing a project of this nature will require the building of partnerships and relationships over time with the local council, local organisations and most significantly, members of the community themselves. Through a participant centred and inclusive approach, the nature of the programme would be determined by participants. I contend that adopting a variety of different methods within a participatory approach will allow flexibility in how I research the project and enable me to remain committed to critical qualitative research through a constructivist epistemology and an interpretivist paradigm. Methodologically, I envisage utilising ethnography and PAR over the lifespan of the project to track its development, ensure participants are front and centre in its development and to enable a continuous process of praxis. This will be an ongoing project without any pre-determined or time-framed research output.

One organisation that can support this project is my employer, the University of the West of Scotland (UWS), whose Ayr campus is situated on the outskirts of Ayr North. There are factors within UWS which would enable it to make a significant contribution to a project of this nature. Firstly, the University has incorporated the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals into its 2025 corporate strategy. Secondly, it has set up a development fund where staff can make a pre-tax financial contribution to the university so that they can invest in projects both within and outwith the university. Thirdly, the university has a wealth of different programmes and institutes that could contribute knowledge, understanding and experience of community engagement. These include my own programme: BA (Hons) Sport Coaching and Development which is based in Ayr and currently has 260 students.

This is not necessarily a project that would exist in the way in which it is originally envisaged. It would be organic, open to continued change and adaption over a number of years and be vulnerable to changing policy objectives and pressures. The project would be long-term and require continuous support and engagement from UWS, South Ayrshire council and the local community. If the local community is to engage successfully then they must be provided with the opportunity to shape and guide the project to meet their own needs and aspirations.

4.2.2 Addressing Inequity

Currently I have an article under peer review in the International Review for the Sociology of Sport. The article entitled *A Global Critical Framework: Analysing and realising social change through sport for development*, critically analyses the value of a global critical framework to the analysis and realisation of social change through sport for development. The article argues that applying a global critical framework to macro level analyses of sport for development would increase understanding of how to address inequity and realise social change outcomes. Following publication of the article I intend to turn the content of this critical appraisal into an

article for submission to the Journal of Sport for Development. The journal is open access and due to focus of the article being on developing education in SfD I believe that publishing it open access will provide a valuable resource in addressing inequity for students, scholars, and practitioners.

Alongside this article I will build upon RPCE (2018) and IJSP (2020) to address inequity through the analysis of macro level issues that impact upon policy and practice at the micro level. This is not to dismiss micro level research, rather, it is about connecting the micro to the macro through determining the wider social, cultural, political, and economic factors that influence inequity in both education and SfD. Specifically, I have plans in place for undertaking a research project that will analyse policy and its impact upon sport, physical education physical activity practice within Scotland since devolution in 1997. This is a significantly under-researched area, and it is important to determine the impact of specific policies across sport, physical activity, and physical education such as the Active Scotland Delivery Plan (Scottish Government, 2018). These different areas are all interconnected within Scotland through the Health and Well-being Outcomes Framework (Scottish Government, 2015) and this provides the rationale for analysing policy collectively across these different areas. In relation to physical education, I predominantly support the holistic and inclusive approach that the Scottish Government has developed. Physical activity levels participation rates amongst adults, however, have remained static since 2008 and there are worrying signs that young people's participation in sport is starting to decline. This position is reinforced through structural inequalities of gender and class in sports participation which appear to be entrenched in Scottish society with little change over the last 10 years despite public policy priorities targeting these groups (Rowe, 2019).

The research will be a mixed method study, similar in approach to IJSP (2020), that will explore the significant amount of quantitative data generated by Sport Scotland and, qualitative

data through interviews with significant stakeholders. Incorporating mixed methods such as policy analysis and quantitative data analysis provides significant value when analysing macro level factors such as sport policy (see IJSPP, 2020; PCET, 2018). There is precedent for this type of mixed method approach to analysing sport policy. Lindsey (2020) analysed policy change and continuity in physical education and school sport policy in England since 2010 and did so through the analysis of sport specific policy and interviews with significant policy actors. The value of the research will be in its analysis of the impact of current policy approaches to sport, physical activity, and physical education in Scotland.

4.2.3 Inclusion for social justice

In this critical appraisal I have evidenced my continued commitment and contribution to inclusive practice and social justice. Inclusive education has been a fundamental principle throughout my career in terms of both my practice and my research. In my belief in inclusion I agree with Ainscow, Chapman & Gunter (2009) in that inclusion must be a never-ending process rather than a simple change of state. It is something which must be continuously fought for to maintain its prominence in both discourse and practice. The rationale for this is that *“today’s cultural form created to solve an emergent problem often becomes tomorrow’s taken-for-granted recipe for dealing with matters shorn of their novelty”* (Ainscow, 2007, p5)

Whilst I have discussed in the previous section the importance of inclusion for social justice in the development of a community sport project, I also intend to explore this further through undertaking research into inclusive physical education in Scottish schools and physical education teacher education (PETE). Within Scotland, inclusion is a fundamental principle of the Curriculum for Excellence (CfE). The CfE is the school curriculum for children aged three to eighteen that aims for all pupils to feel valued and included (Gray, Maclean, and Mulholland, 2012). The transition to an inclusive approach has caused concerns for experienced

practitioners whose pedagogical approach is embedded in more traditional teaching and learning approaches to physical education. It is difficult to embed new practices with established and experienced teachers as they already have the teaching methods and strategies that they believe are successful (Reid and Thorburn, 2011). It is therefore important to explore any real or perceived disconnect between how inclusive teachers believe they are compared to how included the pupils feel (Lieberman, Grenier and Brian, 2019).

Through connecting the policy objectives of the CfE and the reality of practice in relation to inclusion my intention is to connect the macro to the micro. Do the policy objectives manifest themselves in practice through successful policy enactment? Ultimately, the transition to embedding inclusion and social justice in Scottish physical education through the CfE is a process of change. The problem with such a process is that the most critical factor involved in change is dissatisfaction. Without it, resistance to change will likely be greater than the demand for change (Watkins, 2009).

4.2.4 Transformational pedagogy

My published articles have highlighted a commitment to transformational pedagogy. JSFD (2017) and SES (2022) represent my contribution to developing understanding on how critical pedagogy can be successfully applied within SfD. My perspective on the value of critical pedagogy concurs with Suzina & Tufte (2020) in that it remains relevant today as it applies to every situation where a society is confronted with a dispute over the way it wants to protect, produce, and share wealth. Freire's ideas exemplify hope for those interested in promoting social change through dialogue and critical thinking (Cortina & Winter, 2021). Whilst there are potential opportunities for applying critical pedagogy in the community sport project that I envisage in Ayr North, international research into SfD, and critical pedagogy is a long-term aim.

In order to develop my knowledge and understanding of transformational pedagogy, I will focus my attention on physical education teachers' perceptions of learner centred pedagogy in Scotland and its relationship to the CfE. The research will utilise the 7 minimum standards for the implementation of learner centred pedagogy (Schweisfurth, 2015). Learner centred pedagogy embraces the principles of dialogue and criticality and intentionally seeks student input over time with respect to how pedagogical practices are influencing their abilities and willingness to engage (Oliver and Kirk, 2016).

Whilst I am an advocate for learner centred pedagogy based upon 20 years of teaching experience the term learner-centredness is often used loosely and embraces a very wide range of concepts and practices (Schweisfurth, 2015). Practitioners in any educational setting implement any new pedagogical recommendations in a range of ways. These are impacted by the individual circumstances, experience, status, age, gender etc of their students (Thompson, 2013). Considering these variables alongside culture and human capacity, enables us to know where it works, how it works and with whom (Schweisfurth, 2011). The intention, therefore, is to explore the reality of applying learner centred pedagogy in physical education in Scotland and determine the strengths and areas for improvement in practice.

I outline my four-year research plan in Table 4.

Table 4: Four Year Research Plan

Article Focus	Area of Research	Thematic Area	Intended Journal for Publication	Submission
Framework for the design of education programmes in Sport for Development	Sport for Development	Participant Engagement & outcomes	Journal of Sport for Development	2022
Analysis of sport policy in Scotland	Sport Policy	Addressing Inequity	International Journal of Sport Policy and Politics	2023
Understanding and experience of inclusion in physical education in Scotland	Physical Education	Inclusion for Social Justice	European Physical Education Review	2024
Physical Education teachers perceptions of learner centred pedagogy in Scotland	Physical Education	Transformational Pedagogy	Physical Education and Sport Pedagogy	2025

4.3 Summary of the Critical Appraisal

This critical appraisal and the submitted published articles have demonstrated the contribution that my work has made to both education and SfD. The critical appraisal has met the requirements of the programme of research and, the aim and objectives presented in Chapter 1. In the first instance I have critically reflected upon my personal, professional, political, and philosophical experiences and perspectives in sport for development and education. This was

undertaken in Chapter 2 and included reflections on my personal and professional life, my positionality and research philosophy.

Secondly, I critically reflected upon four themes through an appraisal of the published articles and their connection to literature in the field. Specifically, these themes present insights into education and SfD through advancing knowledge about the potential role of both in relation to participant engagement and outcomes, addressing inequity, inclusive practice for social justice and transformational pedagogy. The critical and reflective appraisal of these key themes is within Chapter 3, and demonstrates how my experiences and perspectives have evolved over time alongside the contribution that the articles have made to those four thematic areas. Finally, through building upon the content of the published articles and the knowledge and experiences derived from research and practice in education and SfD, I summarised the key findings from the critical and reflective appraisal and presented future directions for research at the intersection of sport, development, and education.

At the beginning of this critical appraisal I presented this call for action:

If sport practitioners are to be serious about development, they need to figure out what they believe development should be and construct sport programs and education initiatives designed specifically to address these ideals and objectives (Hartmann & Kwauk, 2011, pp. 298).

In response to this I have critically explored four thematic areas which are fundamental to successful design, delivery and analysis of education in SfD. I contend that SfD projects should prioritise participant engagement, directly address inequities caused by power disparities, promote inclusion for social justice and embrace the incremental development of transformational pedagogy. The application of these ideals and objectives will increase the

likelihood that programme outcomes meet the needs and wants of SfD participants and their communities.

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